

Call: HORIZON-HLTH-2021-TOOL-06

Topic: HORIZON-HLTH-2021-TOOL-06-03

Funding Scheme: HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions (RIA)

Grant Agreement no: 101057062

AI powered Data Curation & Publishing Virtual Assistant

Deliverable No. 2.4

Solution Design AIDAVA (G2)

Pending approval by the European Commission

Contractual Submission Date: 31/05/2025

Actual Submission Date: 27/05/2025

Responsible partner: P1—University of Maastricht (UM)

**Funded by
the European Union**

Grant agreement no.	101057062
Project full title	AIDAVA—AI powered Data Curation & Publishing Virtual Assistant

Deliverable number	D2.4
Deliverable title	Solution Design
Type ¹	DEM
Dissemination level ²	PU
Work package number	2
Work package leader	P1-UM
Author(s)	Isabelle de Zegher, P2-b!lo Remzi Celebi, P1-UM Bela Bihari, Daniel Dallos, P9-GND Dominik Steiger, P13 -MID Svetla Boytcheva, P5- ONTO
Keywords	virtual assistant, data curation, solution architecture, knowledge graphs, EHDS, interoperability, health data intermediary

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The work of MID received funding by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SBFI), subvention contract 22.00093, REF-1131-52104.

Supported by a licence waiver from SNOMED International from a period of 2 years (2024 – 2025), on condition that SNOMED CT is not used and/or deployed commercially.

Document History

Version	Date	Description
V1.0	15 April 2023	Submission of D2.3 (Solution Design for G1)
V2.0	2 July 2024	Answer to comments from the reviewers on D2.3: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Comment 1: <i>“Reports a plan for G1 implementation as well as its first evaluation and covers also preliminary discussion on the market analysis of AIDAVA system. The report presents an overall plan, but missing details on the G1 design.”</i> This comment was addressed by revising the Introduction and

¹ **Type:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action):

- R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
- DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
- DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

² **Dissemination level:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action)

- PU: Public, fully open, e.g. web
- SEN: Sensitive, limited under conditions of the Grant Agreement

Version	Date	Description
		<p>Section 4 with the clarification of the difference between G1 and G2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Comment 2: <i>“This deliverable includes figures with unreadable text; the resolution should be corrected.”</i> <p>This comment was addressed by adding the link to the original site with zooming function for Figure 14 and by adapting the size for Figures 15 and 16</p>
V3.0	12 April 2025	<p>First draft of D2.4 of the solution design.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Extraction of most relevant sections from D2.3, of value for developers interested to enhance the solution <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ with updates from D2.3 whenever relevant ○ and in depth editing of Section 4.4. on integration and testing of curation tools ● Complete editing of Section 8 with Go to market approach
V3.1	31 May 2025	Submission

List of Definitions

The definitions used in the deliverable are based on the AIDAVA Glossary [[ref](#)].

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	5
1. Introduction	6
2. Description of Activities	8
3. Problem to be solved and data in scope	10
3.1 Overview	10
3.2 Actors (people and systems)	11
3.3 Type of data sources to be managed	12
4. AIDAVA Solution Design	15
4.1 High level architecture diagram	15
4.2 Backend: foundational repositories & related Epics	16
4.3 Orchestrating automation: onboarding, ingestion, curation, publishing	23
4.4 Non functional Epics	32
4.5 Initiatives and Epics	33
5. Front End : Human in the loop	35
5.1 Principles of user interaction	36
5.2 User profile supporting user interaction during curation	37
6. Formal representation of Solution Design: C4 model	39
6.1 Context level	40
6.2 Container level	41
7. Deployment, Maintenance and Support	43
7.1 Deployment & configuration of the system	43
7.2 Customer support	44
8. Market considerations for the AIDAVA "product"	46
8.1. Expanding & improving AIDAVA through research	46
8.2 Go To Market Analysis	47
9. References	57
10. Annexes	58
A.1 Template of integration & testing specifications	
A.2 Recommendations for deployment of AIDAVA outside of project	

Executive Summary

This document aims to be a reference point for organisations interested in improving and potentially productizing AIDAVA like solutions—after the end of the project—and who need to understand the different elements included in the AIDAVA architecture.

Availability of integrated, high-quality personal health data (PHD) remains limited, with impact on quality & cost of care and limiting possibilities for research and analytics. Indeed, PHD is currently distributed, heterogeneous, captured through different modalities, with variable quality. **F**indability and **A**ccessibility of this data, following the FAIR principles, is addressed in numerous projects; **I**nteroperability and **R**euse remains a challenge due to several factors—heterogeneity, narrative content, inconsistencies, errors...—that are addressed by the intelligent virtual assistant being prototyped in the AIDAVA project. Concretely, the objective of the project is to maximise automation in data curation & publishing³ of heterogeneous PHDs while empowering individuals—patients or their deputies and data curators—when automation is not possible due to lack of contextual information. Through a structured data curation workflow (*Deliverable 2.2. Data curation and publishing process*), the AIDAVA virtual assistant prototype aims to transform each patient's PHD into a Personal Health Knowledge Graph (PHKG). All PHKGs are generated in compliance with the AIDAVA Reference Ontology (*Deliverable 2.1. AIDAVA Reference Ontology as a Global Data Sharing Standard [1]*). From the PHKGs and the mapping information contained in data source description (*Deliverable 3.3. Populated Data Source catalogue for testing*), the publishing module is able to generate different target outputs required by different use cases (see *Deliverable 1.1. Description of Use Cases [2]*).

The AIDAVA prototype is being released in two generations: Generation 1 (G1) was released in June 2024 and assessed in 4 clinical sites (see *Deliverable 1.7. Report on G1 performances*); Generation 2 (G2) will be released in December 2025 and assessed early 2026.

This deliverable builds on the information gathered from G1 (see *Deliverable D2.3 Solution Design for G1 [3]*) to derive the final solution design and Go To Market approach for G2. The high level architecture is similar between G1 and G2, the main difference between the two generations lies in the capabilities and maturities of the data curation tools supporting automation, and the capabilities of the Human-In-The-Loop (HTIL) module.

As a consequence, the first main contribution of this updated deliverable is the description of the integration of newly developed curation tools (see Section 4.3). While the HTIL components are being drastically improved in G2, it does not change the overall architecture and therefore there is no update in this document; more details on HTIL can be found in *Deliverable 5.2. Analysis on explainability for different skill levels; delivery of explainability module for G2*. Other sections have been updated following evaluation of G1.

The second contribution of this deliverable relates to the Go to Market approach which has been significantly expanded following lessons learned from G1 and discussion with the AIDAVA Sustainability Advisory Board (*Deliverable 6.8. Recommendations from SAB*)

³ By "**data curation & publishing**" we mean the integration, harmonisation and quality enhancement (curation) and the transformation into a target format (publishing) of multimodal data, collected from various sources, to make it more usable by humans and machines.

1. Introduction

The AIDAVA prototype consists of a **frontend** and a **backend**.

The **backend** includes foundational components such as the user directory, a master data reference repository, the catalogue of data sources with metadata enabling automation, a library of curation tools triggered when relevant in the automation workflows, the reference ontology serving as standard of reference for the PHKGs, the repository of patient data—from raw data sources to integrated PHKG and published data in the target standard—and the overarching orchestration module that supports automation and interaction with the end users.

The **frontend** interacts with the end users.

This document introduces the different components of the AIDAVA solution and is intended to serve as a reference point for developers who want to improve and build on top of AIDAVA.

Figure 1. AIDAVA high level architecture

- **Section 2** highlights the different activities that took place to derive the solution design
- **Section 3** builds on the use cases (*Deliverable D1.1*) to confirm the key actors of the systems and the different types of data expected as input.
- **Section 4** builds on the business requirements (*Task 1.3 resulting in Deliverable D1.3 [4] updated in Deliverable D1.9*) and the automation requirements (*Task 2.1 resulting in Deliverable D2.2*) to define the components of the backend.
 - User Directory with metadata on users, supporting tailored user interactions.
 - Master Data repository.
 - Catalogue of data sources with metadata on data sources, supporting automation.
 - Library of data curation tools, including conditions of use.
 - Patient Data store with different levels, from raw data, to PHKG, to published data.

- AIDAVA Reference Ontology, serving as a standard of reference to ensure semantic interoperability across PHKGs.
- Orchestration of the processes including ingestion, automated curation and publishing.

This section then identifies the different initiatives and related Epics to be used by the development team. From a solution design perspective there are no major differences between G1 and G2; the difference lies in the implementation of the curation tools.

- **Section 5** builds on the personas developed in *Task 1.2 resulting in Deliverable D1.2 and updated in Deliverable 1.8* and expands on the high-level requirements for the Human-in-The-Loop (HTIL) interaction developed in *Task 5.3. Human-AI interface pattern library for G2*.
- **Section 6** provides a formal description of the AIDAVA prototype based on the 2 highest levels of the C4 model, expanded in the technical architecture (*D3.1*).
- **Section 7** describes the deployment approach as well as the proposed customer support model to be implemented when evaluating the prototype across the different sites. This model was successfully implemented during evaluation of the G1 prototype and will be reused for the evaluation of the G2 prototype.
- **Section 8** develops the Go To Market approach. While G1 evaluation demonstrates the potential for automation in data curation, it also shows several shortcomings that will be solved in G2 but will require additional improvements before productization can be considered. AIDAVA is limited to 2 therapeutic areas and 3 languages; this should be expanded. The AI curation tools identified in this project should be improved, mainly around multi-linguality. Mostly, the AI Act [5] is imposing constraints that require additional work in an uncharted territory. Our first focus in the Go To Market approach is therefore the research community interested in expanding and improving AIDAVA. Section 8.1 provides a detailed description of the tasks needed to expand, deploy and test AIDAVA to other therapeutic areas and other countries with other languages. Section 8.2 is developing a market analysis building on the recommendations from the AIDAVA Sustainability Advisory Board (SAB), *Deliverable 6.8. Recommendations from the SAB* and taking into account two critically important regulations, the European Health Data Space (EHDS) regulation—approved in February 2025, enforced as of March 2025 and gradually implemented—and the AI Act approved in April 2021 and to be enforced as of August 2026. More specifically this section explores the conclusion from the SAB that ***AIDAVA has the potential to become a key element to enable implementation of interoperability within the EHDS and more specifically the 6 critical categories of data to be exchanged in EEHRxF format.***

2. Description of Activities

This document is the result of the work performed within Task 2.3.

During Task 2.3 the following activities were performed during the first part of the task; they are detailed in Deliverable D2.3 and summarized here.

- Consolidation of the problem to be solved and scoping of the solution, including type of data sources to be processed (Section 3)
- Validation of conceptual solution design (Section 4), including proposed components of the solution and data processing workflows and clarification of the data privacy requirements defined in Data Management Plan (*Deliverable D4.2*) and the Generic Data Protection Information Assessment (DPIA) checks described in *Deliverable 4.4*.
- Validation of automation potential based on the orchestration of different workflows with supporting tools (Subsection 4.3).
- Human-In-The-Loop and User Interface (Section 5) to maximise clarity when the system requires an answer and integrating different aspects (user profile, workflows supporting automation of data curation, tailored human interaction)
- Formalisation of the solution and transfer of knowledge to the development team through the C4 model (Section 6) and structuring of the solution architecture and the Epics in Agile Initiatives (see Subsection 4.5).
- A first draft of the proposed model for Deployment, Maintenance and Support of the prototype is provided in Section 7.
- A preliminary first analysis of potential customers and potential market.

The second part of Task 2.3, resulting in this updated version of the solution design include the following activities.

1. **Architectural considerations & challenges derived from the G1 evaluation**, expliciting the different stages in a data curation process, from data source onboarding to publishing and reuse⁴ demonstrating the feasibility of automation in data curation following well structured workflows (Subsection 4.3). This enabled the development team in WP3/WP5 to focus on the critical challenges to be solved in G2.
2. **Specification of a formal integration & testing process**, based on documented integration specifications and defined testing of each of the data curation tools to be integrated in the prototype. The approach was discussed in detail during the technical workstream of the Tallin General Assembly (October 2024). It led to the definition of a template for integration & testing specification (see Annex 1). These specifications were developed and validated across the development team—and whenever needed validated with the business team—for the data curation & publishing tools to be integrated in G2, during joint WP2/WP3/WP5 weekly meetings from November 2024 to June 2025 and a face to face workshop in Sofia in April 2025.
3. **Detailed plan for additional deployment and improvement of AIDAVA**. A cross consortium team defined a detailed approach for deploying AIDAVA in other sites supporting further

⁴ Journey of a Data Element to data interoperability and reuse, I de Zegher and R.Celebi, Proceeding of MIE2025, Glasgow 2025 - accepted for publication

improvement, piloting and testing of the solution (Section 8) across other sites, in other languages and for other therapeutic areas.

4. **Identification of “Go to Market” approaches** started within the consolidation of the Key Exploitable Results of the project into a potential “product”, discussed during the business stream of the Tallin General Assembly meeting in October 2024 with the relevant partners of the consortium. The potential of the “product” was further evaluated within the Sustainability Advisory Board during the same General Assembly and led to two recommendations (see *Deliverable 6.8*).

- a. Explore the potential of AIDAVA as a key interoperability enabler for healthcare authorities and healthcare organisations as part of implementation of the EHDS.
- b. Further analysis on how AIDAVA could empower citizens in managing their health data.

Considering the impact of the AI Act on AI related software, such as the data curation tools embedded in the AIDAVA backend, the team agreed that productization of AIDAVA should realistically be delayed by a few years, gaining experience on the requirement of the implementation of the AI Act. Nevertheless, there is value in considering potential markets, customers and deployment models for the 2 different value propositions identified above. This is the core of Section 8.

3. Problem to be solved and data in scope

3.1 Overview

The goal of the AIDAVA project is to increase **I**nteroperability and **R**eusability—following the FAIR principles—of Personal Health Data (PHD) through integration and semantic enrichment of heterogeneous source data within a multimodal personal health knowledge graphs (PHKG) compliant with the AIDAVA Reference Ontology. This will be achieved by maximizing automation in the data curation & publishing process and more precisely by orchestrating complementary AI (and non AI) technologies into a virtual assistant that interacts with the users—patients and supporting expert data curators—when automation is not possible, while adapting to users’ preferences and skill levels.

Existing data curation tools support transformation, integration and quality enhancement are siloed, i.e. they solve a specific curation step (e.g., metadata management by Data Catalogue, transformation by ETL, concept extraction by Text Mining, entity reconciliation by Master Data Management, image feature extraction through Deep Learning, imputation of missing data through statistical methods), when in fact all these steps might be necessary. In some cases, these tools are insufficient (e.g., no semantic enrichment by linking different data sources, limited amount of concepts extracted with Text Mining). As a result, data curation & publishing remains a costly, time-consuming manual process managed by expert data stewards; as a direct consequence, much available PHD is not curated and not reusable in clinical care and clinical research.

AIDAVA proposes to solve the problem by orchestrating multiple AI and non AI curation tools through a structured workflow (see *Deliverable D2.2*) to maximise automation in the transformation of the heterogeneous PHD into a PHKG as displayed in Figure 2. The PHKG is enriched gradually as new data sources are added. A PHKG can in turn be published into multiple different target formats—following different data consumption needs—based on mappings predefined within the AIDAVA Reference Ontology.

Figure 2. Heterogeneous data sources transformed into a PHKG, constrained by the AIDAVA Reference Ontology, and published in different formats⁵.

⁵ Consent management, as indicated in the figure, is crucial both at the input and the output side. At the same time, consent management is not part of the AIDAVA software G1 and G2; it is being solved by consent by study protocol. Consent management is also an orthogonal set of issues with respect to the FAIR principles, an additional dimension

3.2 Actors (people and systems)

Based on the detailed description of the 2 use cases provided in Deliverable D1.1 and additional analysis during regular WP1 meetings, we derived a set of actors, including software systems (in light blue).

User	Roles
AIDAVA Administrator	<p>Responsible for configuring – and testing – the solution with all <u>components reusable across sites</u>, before actually deploying the system in local sites.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perform onboarding of data curation tools for each release of the prototype and test their execution with a set of agreed test data • Define and set-up default template with user profile • Define output of publishing supporting the use cases (extract for Breast cancer registry, extract to compute CVD score, HL7 IP extract to transfer to HDI)
SITE Administrator	<p>Responsible for configuring the solution at local level</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Execute onboarding of local data source in data catalogue • Register and manage local users (based on template user profile) • First level support
SITE Source System	<p>System – Hospital Information System – in production on a local site that includes Data Sources to be curated in AIDAVA. Whenever applicable, there must be a Data Sharing Agreement (DSA), including technical Data Transfer Specification (DTS), for each Source system to support transfer to AIDAVA.</p>
HDI – as Source System	<p>Health Data Intermediary (HDI) is an organisation providing an intermediary service to a local hospital and its users, the patients. It enables patients to share personal Data Sources generated outside of the hospital (e.g. GP data, patient reported outcomes or wearable and other medical devices) to be curated in AIDAVA. There must be patient consent and a DSA/DTS between an HDI and the hospital to enable transfer of data from the HDI to the AIDAVA prototype deployed within an hospital.</p>
Patient	<p>As data curators, patients ingest their personal data from the different systems, initiate the curation process and answer questions from the system whenever needed.</p> <p>As data consumers, the patients request to forward their personal data to the local HDI for further visualisation.</p> <p><i>Note: Before using the AIDAVA prototype, the patients need first to sign an Informed Consent Form (ICF) by which they agree that the system will access and process their personal data, and that curators will also have access to their personal health data. This ICF also allows the patient to stop using the system at any point in time. In this case, their personal data included in the system will be either transferred to them or deleted.</i></p>
Curator	<p>The expert curator (also called data steward in some sites) supports patients in the curation of their data, with the consent/agreement of the patient. Whenever a patient is not able to answer a question, the system will automatically send the open question to the assigned curator.</p> <p>This role is a precursor of the “social data worker” that will be further expanded in <i>Deliverable D4.12. Proposed operating model for HDI</i>, and considered as critically important to ensure digital equity of AIDAVA at societal level where some citizens will not be able or interested in managing</p>

User	Roles
	their data and its quality and therefore might not experience the same quality of care.
Data User	Data scientist, health care provider, scientific staff having access to extract published from AIDAVA (with patient consent). More specifically in the context of AIDAVA we have 2 types of data uses. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Breast Cancer specialist who can perform analytics on a "Breast Cancer" registry spread across the 3 sites Cardiovascular specialist who has access to an automatically computed risk score (instead of having to compute it manually) and can more effectively monitor CVD risks.
HDI – as Data User System	Health Data Intermediary (HDI) linked to a hospital can also consume data extracted from AIDAVA. For this, the DSA/DTS between an HDI and the hospital referred previously should be directional: transfer of data from HDI to AIDAVA deployed in the hospital, and transfer of data from AIDAVA to the HDI. For the prototype, the data to be transferred from AIDAVA to the patient-personal encrypted accounts within HDI are expected to include the content of the International Patient Summary (IPS) in HL7 FHIR format and the PHKG in RDF format.
AIDAVA VA	Virtual assistant supporting the user with a maximum of automation and requesting information only when needed.
Research Associate	Dedicated staff within hospital sites, coordinating the evaluation of the research prototype within each hospital. They are responsible for enrolling the patient, providing information needed for configuring the system to each contributing patient and supporting them throughout the evaluation.

3.3 Type of data sources to be managed

Following the use cases, we identified the list of data sources considered as relevant to support the use case (see *Deliverable D1.4—Annex 1—Study Protocol. Section 10*). While the end objective of AIDAVA is to integrate all patient data sources, this allowed the team to focus the research prototype on a subset of the dossier.

The following data sources are expected to be used to support the use cases.

Source	Subcomponent	Short description on information use	Breast Cancer	Cardio
EHR	Discharge Summary/ Discharge letter	A handover document that explains to other healthcare professionals why the patient was admitted, what has happened to them in hospital, and other information needed to continue care	YES	YES
	Medical history	A record of information about a person's health. A personal medical history may include information about allergies, illnesses, surgeries, immunizations, and results of physical exams and tests.	YES	YES
	Progress notes	Progress notes are intended to provide an updated analysis of a patient's condition and progress during treatment.	YES	YES

Source	Subcomponent	Short description on information use	Breast Cancer	Cardio
	Prescribed medications	A prescription drug is a pharmaceutical that requires a medical prescription to be dispensed and their full list is provided usually at the end of a therapeutic encounter.	YES	YES
	Medical imaging reports	Contains the interpretations of images with the main goal of presenting the outcomes of the imaging procedure (e.g. for BC—MRI, Mammography, Ultrasound, PET CT/Tomography and for CVD: Cardiac CT, cardiac echo, coronagraphy, scintigraphy of the patients to physicians)	YES	YES
	Medical images	Confirmed critical ones: Mammography (20 MB/patient for 4 images) and Cardiac echo (1-2 GB in DICOM format per patient)		
	Pathology reports	Contains morphological description, diagnosis, predictive and prognostic factors of tumour and pTNM. Includes reports of cytological specimens, biopsies and surgical specimens	YES	NO
	Surgical procedure descriptions	Detailed description of surgical procedure contains type(s) and extent of surgery, specimens removed and intraoperative pathology consultation report	YES	NO
	Multidisciplinary meeting reports	Multidisciplinary meeting reports contain information about staging, treatment indications and decisions.	YES	NO
	TNM staging	TNM staging describes stage of tumour	YES	NO
	Patient referral document	Patient referral documents contain information about current symptoms and disease, medical imaging. In some cases it can be on paper.	YES	NO
	Laboratory reports	Describe the results of laboratory tests performed for the patient samples	NO	YES
	Echocardiography report	Echocardiography is a diagnostic tool for diagnosis and follow-up of heart disease and its report provides the interpretation of the medical imaging procedure	NO	YES
	Coronary angiography report	Coronary angiogram is a procedure that uses X-ray imaging of the heart's blood vessels and its report provides the interpretation of the medical imaging procedure	NO	YES
	Ambulance record	A record of care provided during the ambulance stage of treatment.	NO	YES
	Emergency department record	A record of care provided during the emergency department stage of treatment.	NO	YES
	ICU/CICU progress notes	Provide an updated analysis of a patient's condition and progress during the ICU stay.	NO	YES
Health Data intermediary	GP record	Contains notes and information from the GP on conditions, lab results, allergies, prescriptions. It is less detailed than any information contained in the EHR. As GP records typically cover the lifetime of a patient, they are offering a truly longitudinal perspective.	YES	YES
	Personal App	Quality of Life Questionnaire (EQ-5D 9 QALY) running on a smartphone -	YES	NO

Source	Subcomponent	Short description on information use	Breast Cancer	Cardio
	Connected medical device	Certified digital devices that help gather vitals (and potentially many other parameters) directly from the patient. One approved medical device will be identified for this use case.	NO	YES

The different data interoperability issues that can be found across these data sources—and should be solved in AIDAVA—are described in *D2.2. Data curation and publishing process*.

	Example	Description (and where it is coming from)
1. Unstructured	Discharge summary GP record Clinical reports/notes	Reports with clinical narratives; either typed directly by a clinical staff or – most often – auto generated from different parts of the dossier
2. Semi-structured	Medical history	Data resulting from capture by a human – contains a combination of free text, numeric and coded values
3. Structured (small)	Lab results Medical device (limited data points)	Data resulting from procedures executed by a machine and providing data in specific format
4. Structured (Image – DICOM)	<i>Rx</i> <i>MRI</i>	<i>Data resulting from reports on imaging</i>
5. Structured (large – TBytes)	Medical device (movelets)	Out of scope for AIDAVA
6. Structured (OMICS)	Genomics Metabolomics	Out of scope for AIDAVA

4. AIDAVA Solution Design

4.1 High level architecture diagram

Figure 3. Architectural overview of the AIDAVA prototype

The AIDAVA prototype architecture includes the following components.

1. The backend includes
 - a. foundational data- and metadata repositories of the system (Section 4.2)
 - b. the orchestration module that is responsible for automation (Section 4.3)
 - c. the human-in-the-loop decision support and explainability module enabling adaptive interaction – with explanations – with the user (Section 5)
2. The Admin functionalities support the system administrator to configure the system to maximise automation and user adaptability (included in Section 4.2)
3. The End User functionalities support user interaction around ingestion, curation and publishing (included in Section 4.3) as well as the one related to explainability (Section 5)
4. APIs that support ingestion from connected data sources (Section 4.4)
5. APIs and additional functionalities that support the publishing of data (Section 4.4) including
 - a. the IPS viewer, provided by Partner MIDATA
 - b. an extract to compute the SMART CVD score
 - c. an extract to generate the local BC registry

These components are described in the sections below.

Difference between Generation 1 (G1) and Generation 2 (G2) of the AIDAVA prototype

The main difference between G1 of the prototype and G2 lies in two aspects

- **Quality of curation tools** included in the library of curation tools. In G1, they were either open-source tools or very early prototypes—with limited training and testing—of the new tools being developed in the project. For instance, in G1, for extraction of structured data from narrative in Dutch and Estonian for which there is no good NLP tool available yet, data sources

in these languages were first translated in German with an open-source tool and then processed with the AVERBIS NLP tools processing German text. In G2, we will deploy NLP tools developed and tested during the project that are able to process Estonian, Dutch as well as German language directly.

- **User interaction.** In G1 of the AIDAVA prototype, development focused on the overall front-end interface while user interaction triggered by a data curation issue was limited to a question without context and explanations. In G2, the user interface will build on advanced technologies from human-computer interaction—including leveled explainability—to facilitate understanding of the questions raised by the virtual assistant during the curation process. Explanations will be tailored to users categorised through different user profiles as identified in *Deliverable D1.2. Report from user survey with personas canvas*.

4.2 Backend: foundational repositories & related Epics

4.2.1 User Directory and User Management

There are two main types of users

- The administrators, the patient and the local curators, identified as persons with their personal credentials. (Note: local data curators will automatically be assigned to the Curator role for the patients in the context of the prototype and following signature of the Informed Consent Form by the patient).
- The data users: they can be an organisation or an individual acting in a specific role but not as a private individual. They should provide credentials as data users, not as private individuals

COMPONENT	<p>USER DIRECTORY</p> <p>Repository which contains data related to the users of the systems (including administrators) with the following information.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Default profile & roles (type of role is defined at AIDAVA level across sites): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Specification of the role with related access rights (i.e access to different functional components) ○ Template profile of typical users of the system – based on Personas identified in Task 1.2 – with their roles and related access rights ● User profile of each registered user (provided at Site level) with <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Identification information that allows to uniquely identify the user – including <i>a pseudonym to be used when processing individuals' data and supporting linkage across data sources</i>. ○ Information about the user relevant in the context of data curation (e.g. skill set including health literacy and digital literacy) ○ Specification of default profile of the user as well as their preferences for enabling adaptability in the interaction; the user profile should be updated as the system – through the explainability module – learns from the interaction with the user
EPIC	USER MANAGEMENT

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>AIDAVA Administrator</i>: Define/manage templates with different user profiles and related access rights, based on roles (AIDAVA admin level). Typical user profiles are described in the AIDAVA personas (D1.2/D1.8) ● <i>Site Administrator</i>: Manage registration and update of local users by linking the user with a default profile and confirming access right based on their role ● <i>AIDAVA VA</i>: Creates the root PHKG with identification information about the patient and core identifiable information such as gender, ethnicity... ● <i>End user (patient, expert curator, data user)</i> is able to manage /update their preferences <p>USER INTERACTION</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Login into the system ● Support dialogue with the user to capture information needed to advance the workflow (G1 = simple dialogue, G2 = dialogue with explanations) ● The number of questions raised to the patient/data curators should be limited (e.g. for NLP output need to specify an upper limit of number of questions per data source). Whenever user input is required, the AIDAVA prototype will <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ decide if the question should be raised to the patient or to an experienced data curator based on the type of question and skill set of the user ○ provide explanations to the patient and user – at their level of understanding according to their profiles
Assumptions for the prototype	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The prototype will come with predefined user profiles defined at AIDAVA level across sites ● User accounts—for Patients, Curators, Data Users described in Section 3.2—will be created when the system is deployed in each site, following an information session with the research associate, specifically for the patient and the curator, during which he/she will be asked to answer a questionnaire to assess their skills (e.g. medical and computer literacy) that will drive user interaction. Additional aspects such as preferences of interaction and language will also be added when creating the user account.

4.2.2 Master Data repository and Master Data Management

COMPONENT	<p>MASTER DATA REPOSITORY</p> <p>Represents data about the business entities that provide context for business transactions across multiple systems & data sources</p> <p>They are typically used as a "look up" table and are dynamic, i.e. business entities can be added on an ongoing basis. This information is important to support entity deduplication of master data (e.g., name of a Healthcare Provider) .</p> <p>In AIDAVA, there are different types of "master" business entities</p>
------------------	--

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisations which can be a hospital or a department within a hospital, • Health care person, i.e. staff that intervene at different points in time in the life of a patient within the organisation. <p>Master Data will be managed directly by the Site Administrator i.e. they are downloaded from the local site in an agreed format and transferred into AIDAVA before deployment of the prototype.</p> <p><i>Note: This information is already available in certain countries where users can query a central database. As part of the deployment of the European Health Data Space (EHDS), this information should increasingly be available at regional and national level, hopefully properly curated and in a standardised format that can be easily reused.</i></p>
EPIC	<p>MASTER DATA MANAGEMENT</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Site Administrator updates the repository with relevant information for the site before starting the evaluation, as part of the system configuration. • In addition, the Site Administrator should be able to update the repository during the evaluation/running of the application, if/when a new occurrence of an entity is detected.
Assumptions for the prototype	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information about the local hospital and the related HDI will be entered manually when deploying the system on the local site • Information about the health care professionals active in the TA within the hospital will be entered as well when deploying the system on the local site. However, we cannot expect that all HCP identified in the patient medical record will be included; the system will allow the data curator to add new HCPs if/when a new occurrence is detected.

4.2.3 Catalogue of Data Sources and Data Source Onboarding

COMPONENT	<p>CATALOGUE OF DATA SOURCES</p> <p>The data sources in scope are listed in Section 3.3. Data Sources of a single patient are coming from the Hospital as well as from the HDI through asynchronous file transfers, compliant with the schema provided in the Data Transfer Specification (DTS) mentioned above. Each data source is described in detail in the Catalogue of Data Sources.</p> <p>This catalogue includes metadata on the data sources that need to be curated. The required metadata has been identified in <i>Deliverable 2.2 Details on curation and publishing process</i>. The data source catalogue has been implemented following the DCAT-AP [6] standard used in the EHDS as “Data Description” [7]; it extends on the definition of the EHDS Data Description with technical metadata on the data source schema.</p> <p>This catalogue is critical in supporting the automation of the curation process. Indeed, the metadata allows to identify the interoperability issue of the source</p>
------------------	--

	component to be curated and to map each data item either with a concept in the AIDAVA reference ontology or with a specific curation workflow (and related tools) that enable derivation of structured concepts.
EPICS	<p>DATA SOURCE ONBOARDING</p> <p><i>Site Administrator:</i> onboard data sources following workflow described in Deliverable D2.2 and update the catalogue of data sources with all descriptors (i.e. metadata) of the data sources to maximise the potential for automation. See Section 4.3.1 for details on the onboarding process.</p>
Assumptions for the prototype	The Catalogue of Data Sources is deployed and updated when the AIDAVA prototype is deployed within a local site. The Catalogue must be fully updated with relevant metadata before the curation starts; if not, the curation process for the data source for which the catalogue is not complete will not execute properly and the content of the data source will not be included.

4.2.4 Patient Data store

COMPONENT	<p>There are 4 levels of data stores, with different versions of the same data.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● RAW DATA. The RAW Data stores source data as received, in any electronic format (could be SQL dump or any type), following the DTS mentioned above. ● STAGING area (Source Health Knowledge Graph—SHKG). The Staging Area stores data sources being processed up to the curated format in knowledge graph / RDF format. Each source knowledge graph (SHKG) is then integrated within the individual's Personal Health Graph (PHKG) and transferred to the Curated Data Store when all issues related to integration across data sources have been solved. ● CURATED area (Personal Health Knowledge Graph—PHKG). The Curated Data is stored in the integrated PHKG of each individual patient. ● PUBLISHED area. Stores any type of data (personal identifiable data as well as pseudonymized/anonymized data in structured format) derived from the patients' PHKG in response to a specific data request. Note: In the prototype we will keep the published data to ensure auditability. In the long term, we could keep just the query to recreate the extract
------------------	--

	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 4. The 4 types of data stores in AIDAVA</i></p>
<p>EPIC</p>	<p>This component is used in the INGESTION and CURATION Epics</p> <p>In the context of the Data Curation, functionalities can be limited to data storage and -retrieval functions. (Automatic) archival should be included in a later stage.</p>
<p>Assumptions for the prototype</p>	<p>Empty at deployment time</p>

4.2.4 Library of curation- and publishing tools, and onboarding of tools

COMPONENT	<p>LIBRARY OF CURATION & PUBLISHING TOOLS</p> <p>This is a library of tools to support the data curation & transformation process. Several tools related to matching & ranking and ETL are long-standing existing products on the market; AI-based tools are emerging. This list is expected to be constantly updated: the wider and more powerful the tools, the more automation potential can be achieved without the need for user interaction.</p>
EPICS	<p>TOOL ONBOARDING</p> <p><i>AIDAVA Administrator</i> integrates data curation & publishing tools —after due module and integration testing— belonging to a curation workflow and triggered by the system to perform specific curation steps to solve data interoperability issues (see <i>D2.2. Data curation and publishing process</i>).</p> <p>This includes the following</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Update the library of curation tools for any tool for which a need has been identified in the curation and publishing process • Integrate the tool so that it can be executed from the curation and publishing workflows with the appropriate input and return the appropriate output <p>In case of error, the system should return the name of the tools with the provided input data and any additional information to support resolution</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Test the tool and its integration
Assumptions for the prototype	<p>In AIDAVA, this library will contain</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • for G1: existing products/open-source software identified in Task 2.1 and whenever needed very early prototype of tools being developed for G2 • for G2: same as G1 where some tools are replaced with novel tools developed and tested in the project

4.2.6 Reference Ontology and Reference Ontology Management

COMPONENT	<p>Reference Ontology</p> <p>Components – supported/ implemented within AIDAVA as described in <i>Deliverable 2.1. AIDAVA Reference Ontology as a Global Data Sharing Standard</i>)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The AIDAVA Reference Ontology is the <u>machine-usable format</u> – in Resource Description Framework (RDF) and maintained in GraphDB from Partner Ontotext – representing the semantics of the concepts defined in the domain in scope of the 2 uses cases of AIDAVA and expressed mainly in SNOMED CT and LOINC. It is based on the Swiss Personal Health Network (SPHN) ontology schema⁶, updated by the AIDAVA ontology experts. It includes the CORE ontology and any extension needed for target format mapping. It is used to ensure interoperability across different data sources and to facilitate data exchange.
------------------	--

⁶ <https://sphn.ch/2023/03/20/sphn-dataset-rdf-schema-2023-release/>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The SHACL rules – also managed within GraphDB – include additional constraints on the concepts – typically scientific/medical constraints (e.g. a biological woman cannot be diagnosed with prostate cancer) related to the domain in scope, resulting from the consensus of scientific societies, and formalised within the Ontology to ensure consistency across data. Implementation of SHACL rules is further described in <i>Deliverable 5.1. Data Quality check services</i>.
EPICS	<p>REFERENCE ONTOLOGY MANAGEMENT</p> <p>The AIDAVA Administrator must be able to upload the reference ontology (<u>including potential updates with version control</u>) and ensure integration with the rest of the system to support data sources onboarding, ingestion, curation and publishing.</p>
Assumptions for prototype	<p>The content of the AIDAVA Reference Ontology is expected to evolve throughout the project, following the governance mechanism described in Deliverable D2.1, and through G1 and G2 of the AIDAVA prototype.</p> <p>The 2 generations of the prototype will therefore be deployed with the last version of the ontology with the components needed for the supported use cases.</p> <p>The governance process to update the AIDAVA Reference Ontology is defined in <i>D2.1 AIDAVA Reference Ontology as the basis for a Global Data Sharing Standard</i>. It is expected that the AIDAVA Reference Ontology will require further maintenance and mainly alignment with other standards and ontology to maximize sustainability—and reuse of AIDAVA. This is further discussion in Section 8.</p>

4.2.7 Utilities Management

COMPONENT	NA
EPICS	<p>UTILITIES MANAGEMENT</p> <p>The systems should allow for metrics and benchmarks on usage on the following components</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Catalogue / Data Source Data Catalogue / Curation Metadata Library of Data Curation tools Results of Quality Assessment
Assumptions for the prototype	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support the admin users of the systems to visualise the quality of the PHKG based on quality metrics Support the generation of the BC registry and federated queries across BC data stores ("BC registry") across the 3 hospitals Support publishing of the IPS in HL7 FHIR format

4.3 Orchestrating automation: onboarding, ingestion, curation, publishing

The automation process implemented and being tested in the prototype is outlined in Figure 5. It illustrates the journey of a data element (DE) moving from data collection to secondary use. This journey includes several stages grouped in three logical phases following Data Source Generation:

1. Data Source Onboarding,
2. Data Source Curation and Quality Enhancement which include ingestion and curation, and 3)
3. Publishing for Secondary Data Use.

In this section, each stage is first described in detail. This description is followed by:

- a short description of the related EPIC where this stage is being developed,
- the set of assumptions we made while developing the prototype,
- a detailed analysis of related the data flows (and need for privacy and consent based on the level of identifiability of the data), and
- finally recommendations to accelerate sustainability.

Figure 5. Journey of a data element toward interoperability and reuse.

4.3.1 Data Source onboarding

Description

Data Source Onboarding relates to the description of the raw data sources; it does not involve personal data and does not touch on data privacy. It results in the update Data Source Catalogue (see Section 4.2.3)

Data Source Onboarding includes two stages on data source description.

- **Documented**, i.e all the information needed to understand the format and content of each data element (DE) in the data source is provided. Even for unstructured narratives, providing context on the content significantly improves the accuracy of NLP tools. Documentation includes source level creation metadata (i.e., information about how and where the data was generated) and technical representation metadata (e.g., format and restriction on data). In health organisations, many of which rely on information systems that may be over 30 years old, this documentation is often incomplete and/or missing.

- **Mapped.** The second stage is mapping.
 - Semi-structured DEs are either pre-processed into several structured data that are mapped to concepts in the ontology and/or associated to the entity linking tool, an AI tool performing automatic medical coding.
 - DEs with unstructured narratives are associated with an NLP tool.
 - Structured DEs are mapped into a concept described in the reference ontology; this includes specification of transformation (e.g., unit conversion, link to another value set or coding systems). Defining mappings requires a combination of advanced health literacy and in depth understanding of the ontology engineering; few individuals possess both skills at the needed level. In addition, variability in human interpretation can lead to inconsistencies in the mappings which impede interoperability. To minimise the difficulty and risk of inconsistencies, the AIDAVA team developed prototype tools to support semi-automated mapping (see Section 3.2.3 in *Deliverable D3.3 Populated Data Source Catalogue*).

Related Epic: DATA SOURCE ONBOARDING

Assumptions for the prototype

Before deploying AIDAVA, a Data Sharing Agreement (DSA) needs to be signed among the different parties: hospital system to hospital-based AIDAVA prototype (if relevant); hospital-based AIDAVA prototype and Health Data Intermediary / HDI.

- **Documented data source.** The DSA includes a Data Transfer Technical Specification (DTS) with detailed metadata which are stored by the local site administrator at deployment time in the Catalogue of Data Sources described in Section 4.2.3.
- **Mapped data source** The DTS serves as the basis for the onboarding and mapping process of the data sources following the workflow described in Deliverable *D2.2 Details on curation and publishing process*.

Data Flows

Figure 6. Legend used in the data flows

Figure 7. Building the Data Source Catalogue: onboarding data sourced from a hospital

Figure 8. Building the Data Source Catalogue: onboarding data sourced from a HDI

Recommendations toward sustainability

- **Documented.** Extend EHDS Data Source description to include technical metadata required to support automatic curation.
- **Mapped.** Improve automated mapping tools and develop mapping guidelines following the principles of annotation guidelines, including mapping by two different people and adjudication where there are inconsistencies. This requires the development of a Simple Upper Level Ontology (SULO) that enables alignment of concepts across different ontologies and standards (see Section 8 for more details)

4.3.2 Data Source Ingestion

Description

Data for a single patient is extracted from the source systems with the documentation and mapping defined during onboarding. Ingestion is using the User Directory, the Catalogue of Data Sources and the Raw Data Store.

Note: For paper input from the patient, a "curation workflow" has been defined, starting from the scanning or picture of the paper document, done within the Health Data Intermediary (MIDATA) followed by OCR step and then processing of the content.

Related Epic: INGESTION

Support the patient – or their designated local data curator – to ingest their own personal data from different data sources – in the available format. This includes

- Ingestion of paper-based data sources – by using OCR tools
- Ingestion of electronic data sources available across different data holders such as clinical care providers (hospitals, GP, nursing homes etc.), device- and app providers or Health Data Intermediaries (HDI) mediating data for a patient.

Ingestion of electronic data sources requires a Data Sharing Agreement between the holder of the data sources and the AIDAVA prototype, as well as onboarding of the data sources.

Assumptions for the prototype

For the prototype we will assume 3 types of ingestion (see data flows below)

- Paper documents through OCR
- Data extracted from the Hospital (NEMC, UM/MUMC, MUG) based on the data sources identified in the use cases (see Deliverable D1.1) and agreed DTS; formats can be .csv, .txt, .json, .xml, .pdf, .jpg, .png. No direct integration with a Hospital Information System:
 - Data source onboarding to be performed on the Data Transfer Specification (DTS), with results stored in the Catalogue of Data Sources
 - Data is to be transferred from a hospital into the hospital's AIDAVA secure data store in accordance with the sharing agreement and the DTS.
 - Traffic only possible on agreed channels
- Data extracted from the HDI– based on the data sources identified in the supported use cases, same approach as for hospitals (with DTS and data source onboarding)

Data Flows

Figure 11. Ingestion Flow of Paper Data from the Patient into the PHKG
 (Note: in the AIDAVA prototype, OCR took place within the HDI that shared the resulting PDF with AIDAVA backend)

Recommendations toward sustainability

The AIDAVA prototype was deployed within four hospitals where data sources of consenting patients were ingested. The evaluation follows a structured research protocol. The development and approval of such protocols by local ethics committees is a tedious process not viable for regular re-use of patient data spread across several healthcare organisations.

To decrease the burden related to data privacy, development of new organisations —private of public health services—providing data intermediation services in accordance with the European Data Governance Act acting on behalf of patients who consent to delegate the processing and sharing of all their health data as part of a social contract; sharing should be subject to ethically correct consent.

4.3.3 Data Source Curation and Quality Enhancement

Description

The objective of AIDAVA is to maximise automation in the curation process and to minimise the need for user intervention. Curation is based on workflows, using the catalogue of data sources, the library of curation tools and the patient data stores. During the curation process, the system captures a set of metadata with context information supporting further steps in the automation process

Data sources are curated in 2 steps: independent curation into a specific Source Knowledge Graph (SHKG) and the integration into the Personal Knowledge Graph (PHKG) with consolidation of information and consistency checking

- **Curated (into a Source Health Knowledge Graph—SHKG).** The data elements from an ingested data source can be automatically curated provided that the underlying data interoperability issues are addressed. Eight data interoperability issues (digitisation of paper documents, extraction of structured data from narrative text, format alignment, transformation of semi-structured and structured data, reference data management,

terminology alignment, medical coding, imaging readability) have been identified Deliverable D2.2. Each issue is resolved through a dedicated workflow that calls the appropriate AI—or not-AI—curation tool and initiates a dialogue with a human curator in case the curation tool cannot proceed.

For the eight workflows we identified the need for eleven tools to be included in the Library of Curation tools (OCR, NLP, entity linking, data wrangling, translation, ...). The result of the workflows' execution across all data elements contained in a data source is a Source Knowledge Graph (SHKG) as displayed in Figure 9, representing the content of the data source in compliance with the reference ontology.

Figure 10. Extract of a Source Health Knowledge Graph (SHKG)

- **Curated (& Integrated into the Personal Health Knowledge Graph—PHKG).** Each SHKG must be integrated with the others to form a complete longitudinal record: the PHKG. Integration could result in additional data interoperability issues (e.g., duplication, inconsistency and incompleteness) addressed by associated workflows and curation tools. The most important tool is a data quality check engine implemented through SHACL rules; its challenge is to capture domain and common-sense rules agreed across the health community.

Related Epic: TOOLS ONBOARDING, CURATION, QUALITY MANAGEMENT

Support the patient or their designated local data curator – to curate their personal data and build the patient's Personal Health Knowledge Graph (PHKG) integrating all the data ingested into one common semantic model.

Deliverable 2.2. Data curation and publishing process identified a set of data interoperability issues. Each issue is linked with a workflow that includes one or more tools to be triggered to solve the interoperability issue automatically, if possible. Management of the workflows for the different data sources is done through an orchestration workflow. Automation of curation requires that

- Data sources have been onboarded (see Data Source Onboarding Epic in Section 4.2.3)
- Curation tools have been onboarded (see Curation Tools Onboarding Epic in Section 4.2.4)

In case the workflow requires additional information, the frontend is activated (see User Interaction Epic in Section 4.2.1) to capture the needed information.

Assumptions for the prototype

The system must be able to orchestrate execution of the different workflows for the onboarded data sources and to call on the curation tools included in the library of curation (& publishing) tools.

Data Flows

Three different data flows have been identified

1. Paper ingestion and curation – starting from a hard-copy paper document provided by the patient
2. Electronic file (except for imaging) coming from the hospital
3. Electronic file from the HDI

Figure 11. Curation Flow: HIS/Hospital electronic file to PHKG

Figure 12. Curation Flow: HDI to PHKG

Recommendations toward sustainability

- **SHKG.** Improve capabilities of curation tools, building on the potential of Large Language Models [8] to maximise automation in data curation.
- **PHKG.** Maintain an open-source library with validated data quality checks, ranging from lab results ranges linked to testing instrument calibration to more sophisticated knowledge rules related to diagnosis, therapeutics, drug interactions...

4.3.4 Publishing (identifiable and non-identifiable data)

Description

Publishing is the last and richest stage in the journey of a data element resulting from the extraction, mapping/transformation through SPARQL queries of one or more patient PHKG into an agreed target format. Multiple outputs can be generated from the same PHKG: 1) identifiable subsets such as the six critical datasets in EEHRxF format to comply with the EHDS regulation or specific views to meet the needs of different healthcare specialists; 2) population datasets extracted from multiple PHKGs of consenting patients, like clinical registries or just in time specific real-world data.

Related Epic: PUBLISHING, DATA EXTRACTS

Support the user – patient or any other consented data user – to extract from a patient-specific PHKG, or from a set of PHKGs, a data set that is further transformed into the target format required for the 3rd party application that will use the data set. The extracts generated are kept within the AIDAVA prototype, ready to be shared.

Assumptions for the prototype

In the context of the AIDAVA prototype, the extract will be predefined to support the 3 uses cases

- **Extract 1.** Patient IPS (HL7 FHIR format) extracted from the patient PHKG to be transferred to the personal encrypted data accounts at the HDI – with patient consent. PHKG in RDF format transferred to the personal encrypted data accounts at the HDI - with patient consent
- **Extract 2** (Breast cancer use case). List of data elements identified as part of the "EU breast cancer registry", extracted from the PHKG of the breast cancer patients, in the specified format.
- **Extract 3** (Cardiovascular use case). Data elements needed to compute the SMART score extracted from a patient's PHKG.

Data Flows

There are 2 main workflows

- One for identifiable data for a single patient/ PHKG: (1) extract to be transferred to the HDI and (2) extract to compute the CVD SMART score
- One for non-identifiable data (pseudonymized or anonymized) across multiple patients/ PHKGs to deliver the Breast Cancer Registry at each site

A third export agreed in a later stage of the project is the transfer of the fully identifiable PHKG to the HDI, conforming with the DSA signed between the hospital and the HDI.

Figure 13. Publishing. Single PHKG to identifiable data set for 2 data uses

1. HDI: with HL7 IPS to be transferred
2. Hospital HCP: CVD extract to compute the CVD score

Figure 14. Publishing PHKG to pseudonymized aggregates – to be used for the Breast Cancer extract

4.3.5 Integration and testing of supporting tools

Apart from data source onboarding, the different steps described above are implemented with workflows, supported by different tools. As curation & publishing tools—and certainly AI based tools—are rapidly evolving, AIDAVA has a microservice architecture that enables smooth plug-in, plug-out of the most appropriate tools.

To ensure effective integration, each tool must have a well-documented integration specification and must be tested independently.

- **Integration specification** includes scope, business and technical requirements, assumptions and potential constraints of the tool, input and output. This ensures that all parties share the same understanding on what the tool is expected to deliver.

- **Testing** focuses on module testing only; it includes a description of approach, description of testing data and/or how they will be gathered and made accessible and result of testing execution. It is critically important to execute proper testing before integration to ensure that the tool to be integrated works as expected

An additional aspect to be considered for each of the AI based tools used in AIDAVA is the AI Act, entering into force on 1 August 2024, while enforcement of the majority of its provisions will commence on 2 August 2026. The AI Act requires that the high-risks AI system—as a WHOLE—includes detailed technical documentation (Annex IV of the regulation). AIDAVA is a high-risk AI system and G2 of the prototype will be tested with real patients on site; as the evaluation will take place early 2026, before enforcement of the law, there is no need to comply. We nevertheless included in the integration specification and testing document a set of information that should support compliance.

A template document of the integration & testing specification is provided in Annex 1 and is used as the basis for each tool being integrated.

4.4 Non functional Epics

EPICS	Objectives
Integration	<p>The AIDAVA will function standalone. It will however require data transfer based on a formal Data Sharing Agreement (DSA) with Data Transfer Specification (DTS)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DSA/DTS from the hospital to AIDAVA to support ingestion of patient data ● DSA/DTS from the HDI to the AIDAVA prototype to support (1) ingestion of patient data into AIDAVA and (2) transfer of personal data – in the form of HL7 IPS and of the PHKG– back to the HDI for visualisation and use by the patient <p>In addition, AIDAVA requires the integration of 2 software components</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● A federated query (see Section 3.2.1 in Deliverable D1.4 – Annex with Study Protocol) – to compute parameters across sites – that is to be executed in all 3 sites and to return the consolidated results in each of the 3 sites (Peer to Peer request) ● The SMART score algorithm (see Section 3.2.2 in Deliverable D1.4 – Annex with Study Protocol) that is executed locally and produces a score for the physician (internal in each hospital site)
Audit trail	<p>As the AIDAVA prototype is managing personal data and is intended to become a fully-fledged medical device, any transaction should be linked to an audit trail (who did what when).</p>
Security	<p>As the AIDAVA prototype is managing personal data, the system should support the following requirements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data stored within the hospital environment and transferred following pre-agreed data sharing agreement/ data transfer specification ● Data stored in a secure environment, with no data loss

EPICS	Objectives
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role-based security access: access must be authorised based on access rights (e.g. an administrator should not have access to the personal data of a patient) • Disaster recovery for the prototype – not to be used for clinical care and decision making – this is not critical
Parameters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Performance. Response time: less than 3 seconds • Availability = min 8 hours per day/ 5 days per week (working hours) with 90% to be operational during this period • Reliability/ Mean time between failures (MTBF) = 90% with a Mean Time To Repair (MTTR) of 48 hours
Quality Management	Support the users of the systems to visualise the quality of the PHKG based on quality metrics as introduced in the Study Protocol (Annex 1 of Deliverable 1.4) and to be further detailed in <i>Deliverable 4.6 .Definition of Data Quality metrics & checking rules</i>

4.5 Initiatives and Epics

Figure 15 below groups the different components of the solution architecture, identified in Figure 3, organised in initiatives on which the development team can further concentrate

Figure 15. Grouping of Epics through initiatives

The colour code indicates how the different databases relate to the different initiatives

4.5.1. API initiative

Relates to interfaces to access patients' data from the hospital and HDI, through asynchronous data transfer based on formal specifications. The data transfer specifications of each data source are included in the "Catalogue of Data Sources"; the patient data transferred from the different data sources is stored into the "Patient DS – Raw". API also relates to interfaces transferring published data – and stored in "Patient DS – Published" – to the HDI of the patient.

4.5.2 User Services

Includes documentation and training, as well as User Management (including account management, secure login, user preferences). As part of account management, when registering a patient the "root" part of their PHKG will be created with basic identifiable information such as birthdata, gender, ethnicity. User Services also includes management of the user interaction specifically during the curation process with simple questions for the Generation 1 of the prototype and additional decision support during Generation 2.

This initiative relies on data stored in the User Directory with user profiles and preferences as well as the Patient DS—Curated PHKG.

4.5.3 Ingestion Services

Relates to the ingestion of the different data sources of the patient – documented in the Catalogue of Data Sources – by the patient themselves, or the curator, from the hospital and/or the HDI. In real life, this would activate the data transfer from the data sources (hospital or HDI) within AIDAVA; in the context of the prototype, this will mark the data available in the "Patient DS – Raw" SQL DB as ready to be curated.

4.5.4 Curation Services Onboarding

First part of the curation process: it focuses on entering information needed to support the process with maximum automation.

- The curation tools onboarding Epic is responsible for updating the "Curation & Publishing Tools" library with information on the tools identified in the curation workflows (Task 2.1 and WP5).
- The data source onboarding Epic (by the Site Administrator) ensures updates to the "Catalogue of Data Sources" in each site, with mapping information between the data source and the AIDAVA Reference Ontology (Schema).
- The master data management Epic ensures that master data is properly updated (by the Site Administrator) when deploying the system locally. The Master Data includes parameters (e.g. reference range) that support the execution of SHACL rules.

4.5.6 Curation Services

Relate to the automation of the curation of the patient data stored in the "Patient DS – Raw". Each data source is curated – through different workflows, triggered by the metadata describing this data source in the Catalogue, and executing

the relevant curation tools onboarded previously. Whenever user input is required, the curation workflow manages the user interaction through the User Interaction module (simple in G1, advanced in G2). The curated data source is stored in the "Patient DS – Staging" Triple Store; it is then integrated with the patient’s PHKG, checked for completeness and consistency through the related workflow and then stored in the "Patient DS – Curated" Triple Store. While checking for completeness and consistency, SHACL rules may be invoked.

4.5.7 Publishing Services

Responsible for transforming the data included in the "Patient DS – Curated" triple store (PHKG) into the required target format based on publishing rules contained in the Reference Ontology. The resulting data extracts are stored in the "Patient DS – Published" data store (from where they can be further processed).

4.5.8 Quality Management Services

Relates to the definition and use of quality rules (in the form of SHACL rules) to check and assess quality. Task 4.2/ Deliverable 4.6 is concerned with the definition of these rules, including scientific rules extracted from community-wide consensus scientific guidelines, correctness rules linking measurement values with ranges specified in the Master Data. Quality Management also relates to the definition of an overall quality score of the curated data.

4.5.9 Others

Includes the non-functional requirements (security, performance, traceability, provenance...), the data usage functions related to the use cases (execution of a federated query across extracts from all Breast Cancer patients in the site, computation of the SMART risk score from the patient’s PHKG extract). This initiative also includes the computation of the quality score for data reuse of the patient’s PHKG.

5. Front End: Human in the loop

5.1 Principles of user interaction

We identified different users in Section 3.2; user interaction with the prototype will be different for each of them.

User	Expected user interaction
AIDAVA Administrator	Update information on curation tools (Curation Tools Onboarding) with simple tools (e.g a spreadsheet to be uploaded or a simple user interface) requiring advanced computer literacy and/or programming skills
SITE Administrator	Update information on data sources (Data Source Onboarding) with simple tools/ user interface requiring advanced computer literacy and/or programming skills
Patient	End users for ingestion and curation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● For data ingestion, the UI should be as simple and as intuitive as possible in compliance with user stories described in <i>Deliverable D1.3. Business requirements</i> ● For data curation, the objective of AIDAVA is to maximise automation and to minimise user interaction. Automation is achieved through a set of related workflows defined in Deliverable 2.2. Each workflow includes different steps that can be <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. a call to execute a curation tool b. a decision taken by the system based on context metadata c. a request to an end user, requiring information to further process/curate a data source d. a human decision The last two steps will activate the "Human In The Loop" module that interacts with the end user taking into account the context and the profile of the user.
Curator	
Data User	End users (patient, curator or any other agreed actor) for publishing – based on the same principles as data ingestion

To ensure acceptance and usability, the AIDAVA user interface for the patient, curator and data user must have the following features

- Multi-lingual, supporting at least Estonian, Dutch and German. The Administrator user interface can be in English
- Desktop or mobile/touch based, where interaction through mobile with patients will be prioritised as much as possible. Data Curator and Administrator interfaces can be desktop based.
- Adaptive to different user profiles and skill sets: the explanations provided to the curators (patient and expert curator) whenever automation is not possible and input from the curator is needed, must be adapted to the user profile. Indeed different patients will have different levels of data, health and digital skillset.

To manage user interaction, AIDAVA will take into account the user preferences and the user profile stored in the User Directory.

- The user preferences include information on the user such as preferred type of interaction (smartphone, tablet or desktop), preferred language, request to delegate certain actions (like ingestion or curation) etc.
- The user profile includes information on the role, access rights and skills of the user. The latter is particularly important to direct curation requests to the appropriate user and to tailor explanations during the curation process as described below.

5.2 User profile supporting user interaction during curation

A patient should not be considered as "one size fits all". Patients are first and foremost citizens with different skill sets that will impact their capacity (and interest) to manage and curate their data. One patient can be a medical data scientist, with a high level of health- and computer literacy; another patient can as well be in a profession that does not require much proficiency in health and computers. They are both patients. As a consequence, we decided to link the questions to be raised not to the type of users but rather to the level of skills described in the user profile.

We identified 2 major skill sets (see *Deliverable 1.2./D1.8*)

- Medical expertise (scale 1 to 10). This attribute will be used in the AIDAVA prototype to decide if a question that occurs in the curation workflow can be sent to the patient or should be sent to the expert curator
- Computer literacy (scale 1 to 10). This attribute can be used in the AIDAVA prototype to provide guidance and information to the user in a customised level of technical complexity

Figure 16. Overview of User profile

As part of more extensive work to be done in Task 5.3, we will consider using other attributes such as motivation, frustration and aspirations (all based on a set of predefined values).

As mentioned above, the curation process is based on a set of workflows (see Deliverable 2.2) that

- attempt to curate the data automatically by calling and executing the appropriate curation tools
- request input from the user, whenever the system requires additional semantic information to solve a data curation issue. It can be a missing date for a specific event that is required (as most of health data is time-stamped e.g. date on which a diagnostic was made) or a missing unit of a measurement procedure (e.g. missing unit for blood pressure measurement in the narrative of the physician). This information can only be provided by a human who understands the context of the patient and, for the second example, has some medical knowledge.

AIDAVA is providing two generations of the prototype.

- Generation 1 (G1) is based on existing curation tools. From a user interaction perspective, it is a simple question. The content of questions is described in Deliverable 2.2 as part of the curation workflow. The question is formulated in predefined canned text based on the context of the question, without considering the level of literacy of the users.
- Generation 2 (G2) is expected to be a major improvement on this aspect.
 - It will consider varying digital literacy levels of the users
 - It will comprise **local explanations** aiming to explain why AIDAVA generated a specific output, **global technical explanations** informing about technical aspects of the AI-based AIDAVA app, and **global social explanations** providing information about relevant socio-technical aspects of the AIDAVA app (*see Deliverable D5.2. Analysis on explainability for different skill levels; delivery of explainability module for G2*)
 - It will be implemented with novel tools developed in the project- including basic LLM functionalities.

6. Formal representation of Solution Design: C4 model

The C4 model is a hierarchical approach to software architecture modelling that provides a set of diagrams for visualising the components, containers, and context of a system. It is designed to be simple, lightweight, and scalable, making it easy to communicate and understand the system's architecture across different stakeholders. It is often used in agile and DevOps environments, where quick and efficient communication and collaboration among developers, architects, and stakeholders are essential.

It consists of four levels, where each level represents a different level of abstraction:

1. **Context:** This level provides an overview of the entire system and its interactions with external systems, showing the system's boundaries, users, and external dependencies.
2. **Containers:** This level describes the high-level components of the system and their interactions, showing how the system is decomposed into smaller, more manageable parts.
3. **Components:** This level describes the internal components of each container and how they interact with each other, showing how the components are organised and connected within a container.
4. **Code:** This level represents the lowest level of abstraction, showing how the components are implemented in code.

Figure 17. Levels of C4 description
(see [9] to view details)

This deliverable is focusing on level 1 (Context) and level 2 (Containers), which have been mapped to the solution design described in Section 4.1

The AIDAVA platform will have different types of users as described before (Administrators and End Users). It will take as input either

- a physical paper copy⁷ of the patient's health related documents, that will be scanned by the patient themselves or their relative.
- electronic documents coming from the hospitals or from Health Data Intermediaries; the documents in scope of the prototype are described in Deliverable D1.1.

To support data curation, AIDAVA will use a set of curation tools – managed within the Library of Curation Tools – and integrated into the system as microservices by the AIDAVA Administrator.

AIDAVA will produce different outputs in different formats. For the prototype, this includes

- HL7 IPS of the patient will be transferred to the relevant Health Data Intermediary
- Extract for Breast Cancer registry and SMART CVD score which will remain within AIDAVA for further processing.

The data usage function will include among others

- the algorithm support computation of the SMART risk score for individual patients,
- A federated data query that can be executed across the 3 hospitals participating in the evaluation.

6.2 Container level

AIDAVA will follow a microservice architecture integrated on the publish/subscribe principle.

- **API Gateway:** The API gateway acts as the entry point for all external requests into the microservice architecture. It provides a single point of entry for all external clients, and routes requests to the appropriate microservice(s). The API Gateway can also perform authentication, rate limiting, and other security-related tasks.
- **Event Manager:** The event manager is responsible for managing the communication between microservices. It receives events from publishers, routes them to the appropriate subscribers, and ensures that events are delivered to all interested parties.
- **Services:** Services are the individual components of the microservice architecture. Each service performs a specific business function and can communicate with other services via the event manager. In a pub/sub architecture, services can act as publishers, subscribers, or both. When a service publishes an event, other services that have subscribed to that event will receive it and can perform any necessary actions. The services are responsible for their own data storage, retrieval, and management. Each service encapsulates its own data and provides an API for other services to access it. This means that each service can use the database technology that is best suited to its specific needs, rather than being constrained by a single technology that is used by all services.
- **External systems** will be simulated for the prototype that will access them through an API, with data transfer specification. In the prototype, the API will access files provided asynchronously; for the product, these APIs will need to be changed to allow direct access to the data source.

⁷ Paper documents are still important in certain countries, certainly for legacy documents.

Figure 19. AIDAVA – C4 Container level

7. Deployment, Maintenance and Support

This section describes the deployment of the prototype, which is strictly constrained by a study research protocol. A full product, running in real life, will have to be more flexible and should be more tightly integrated with data holders and data users and offer a wider support (24/7 instead of 8/5).

7.1 Deployment & configuration of the system

Deployment of a prototype solution like AIDAVA – managing sensitive personal data – must be done in a strictly controlled way, to ensure data protection compliance, including the following steps.

7.1.1. Preparation – before deploying the prototype

This phase is being managed within Task 1.4. It is provided here for information.

Step	Description	Coordination with local sites
Research Protocol	Definition of the Study Assessment Protocol (D1.4) with the clinical teams, to be used as the basis of the submission to each local Ethical Committee	NEMC
Data Privacy checks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For the patient, and included as annex to the Study Assessment protocol: Informed Consent Form and Study Information Package validated by the AIDAVA Project Data Protection Officer (DPO – Partner IHD) and translated in the local language for each site Data Privacy Impact Assessment (DPIA) – to be performed in each site – on the basis of an information governance checklist provided by the AIDAVA DPO (Deliverable 4.4) 	NEMC
Data Sharing Agreement (DSA)	Formal contractual agreement between the different parties to share data; a template contract is proposed by the AIDAVA DPO as a basis to be used in each site. The DSA includes a Data Transfer Specification (DTS) which captures detailed information on data sources to be curated; this information is used as the basis of the data source onboarding process. The DSA with the DTS needs to be provided in each site (hospital and HDI) – see integration aspects in Section 4.4.	b!lo
Ethical Committee Approval	Each site will have to submit the Study Assessment Protocol and the DPIA to the local Ethical Committee for approval before starting the actual evaluation. It is expected that this takes between 4 to 6 months and should therefore be done well in advance (i.e. started in Feb 2024 for an evaluation foreseen in Aug 2024)	NEMC
Training	Organisation of training sessions for the different types of users (before and during evaluation)	NEMC

7.1.1. Deployment of the AIDAVA prototype

Step	Description	Lead
Testing and Validation (GND)	Software must be tested and validated within GND and must pass the acceptance threshold	GND
Preparation of Documentation	Details on <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Infrastructure description • Guidelines for installation and configuration – and local testing 	GND
Build and Release	Software is built and packaged into a release package, which includes all the necessary files and artefacts needed for installation. The release package may be stored in a repository, such as a version control system or artefact repository.	GND
Environment Setup	Target environment must be set up with the necessary infrastructure and resources to support the software. This to include setting up the hardware, network connectivity, and software dependencies This includes clarification of the local servers for <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raw data transferred from hospitals and HDI • Curated PHKG (Staging and Curated areas) • Published output for consumption for BC query, CVD score • Published output for transfer to HDI 	Local Admin
Local Configuration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onboarding of different components: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Data Source Catalogue ○ Master Data Repository ○ User Directory with users identified for the evaluation (patients should be added as they are recruited) • Setup of data transfer of patient (HL7 IPS) data back to the HDI for further use and visualisation 	Local Admin
Testing and Validation	The software must be tested and validated in pre-production environments <u>locally</u> to ensure that it works as expected and does not cause any issues or conflicts with existing systems.	Local Admin

7.2 Customer support

Level	WHO	WHAT	HOW
L1	Site Admin	<p>Initial level of support provided to users locally – taking into account local constraints and data privacy. It typically involves basic troubleshooting and issue resolution. The goal is to resolve customer issues as quickly and efficiently as possible</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Answer common questions, provide instructions, or direct customers to self-help resources. • User management: add, update or delete user profiles <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Register new user – including personal address – with role and respective access rights; allocate users to roles ○ Take care of users who forgot their password • Log request in Issue Log when not possible to solve the 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal email, chat, or phone • Local language • 8 to 5 local time, working days <p>Input in Issue Log, required when transferring to L2</p>

Level	WHO	WHAT	HOW
		<p>problem directly, and follow up on resolution</p> <p>Note: to send an email from the local site, the AIDAVA local system needs to have access to the local email server (or to have a local account from the hospital email system)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transfer issue to level 2 when not possible to solve locally 	
L2	GND	<p>Involves more complex issue resolution and may require specialised technical knowledge or expertise. Level 2 support is usually provided by a specialised team, such as a technical support team or an engineering team, and may involve more in-depth troubleshooting or debugging</p> <p>Note: need access to the local version: console level access / IP Secure access with admin rights for maintenance purposes => GND will be an agreed stakeholder (as defined in the Study Protocol)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Email and GND phone (remote support with local access) • English • Working days – 8 to 5 local times (CET and CET + 1) = 8 to 6 (CET+1) for GND (NOT 24/7)
L3	GND	<p>Involves the most complex and critical issue resolution, such as bug fixes or product enhancements. Level 3 support is usually provided by the product development team or senior technical experts and may involve code changes or product updates.</p>	
L2	HDI	<p>For issues related to access to personal records (IPS) sent to the HDI</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Email • English • Working days – 8 to 5 local times (CET and CET + 1)

Function	Description	Value (min-max)
Issue Log	<p>Centralised Service management system to be provided by GND to register and track all the issues</p>	<p>GND will provide a central issue tracking system to collect and supervise the issues reported during the evaluation and feedback phase. Also we will provide an issue collector page into the system, which will let the users create issue tickets directly into the tracking system.</p>
Time to resolution	<p>Time it takes between the first entry of an issue in the log file and the resolution</p>	<p>4 hours in average (for the tools developed by GND, no engagement for tools developed by other parties such as curation tools)</p>

8. Market considerations for the AIDAVA "product"

The evaluation of the G1 prototype demonstrated the potential for automation in data curation. While many shortcomings identified in G1 will be solved in G2 (to be deployed by end 2025), improvements—including extension to other therapeutic areas, other languages and compliance to the AI Act—will be needed. Our first “Go To Market” step is therefore to support further deployment and evaluation of the solution outside of the project (and after the project) as described in Section 8.1, while Section 8.2 is developing a preliminary market analysis building on the recommendations from the AIDAVA Sustainability Advisory Board (SAB).

8.1. Expanding & improving AIDAVA through research

Deployment and evaluation of G1 of the AIDAVA prototype demonstrating the feasibility of a new approach to the longstanding problem of data curation of heterogeneous health data. It also documented critical areas to be developed to ensure successful adoption and use of AIDAVA-like solutions.

- Alignment of the **AIDAVA Reference Ontology** with other standards and ontologies to facilitate—and potentially automate—consistent mapping of structured and unstructured health data sources. This requires a Simple Upper Level Ontology (SULO) that supports semantic alignment of different standards needed to support the mapping. A first version of SULO has been developed in the project; its use will be tested with external stakeholders and standard organisations at the end of 2025 as part of a 1 day hackathon (planned early December, satellite meeting of the IHD annual conference).
- Readily available documentation—with technical metadata on the schema—of the raw data sources into a standardized **Data Source Description** format, to ensure that mapping properly reflects the semantic of the data. This could be included as an extension of the emerging Data Description standard of the EHDS⁸.
- Improvement of AI based data **curation tools** such as multilingual NLP, entity linking to SNOMED medical coding, entity deduplication. This is an area of ongoing research across multiple teams and can be done independently of AIDAVA development; the micro-service architecture of AIDAVA enables easy integration of any new tools providing integration requirements are met.
- **Compliance to the AI Act** on which there is little experience, certainly in a multi-modules environment including several AI based tools.

All these aspects require further research, most of them outside of the control of AIDAVA but where AIDAVA can influence. Our first objective is therefore to encourage other teams to further expand and improve on AIDAVA—and AIDAVA like approach—by providing a set of clear guidelines on development, extension and deployment. This is the purpose of the “*Deployment approach of the AIDAVA G2 prototype. Description, benefits, limitations and work plan*” document provided in Annex 2. This document first introduces the AIDAVA prototype: its objective, main components and status. It then describes its benefits as well as its limitations. The last section provides a detailed list of the steps needed for the deployment of the AIDAVA prototype, and potential support services during execution.

⁸ Public consultation - <https://tehdas.eu/public-consultations/>

The document is intended for any research project that requires curated data, and for any healthcare organisation (hospital, national authorities, ..) that wants/needs to transform its data—typically in heterogeneous format and narrative text—into an interoperable format, for reuse in the context of care with extraction and generation of EEHRxF standards like IPS, research with extract of OMOP or CDISC compliant format and public health or policy-making with different formats.

8.2 Go To Market (GTM). Preliminary Analysis

Although AIDAVA has much potential to become a high-value solution in healthcare, the problems mentioned above (lack of semantic alignment between standards, lack of solid documentation of data sources, limited quality of AI curation tools and AI act compliance) drastically limit its viability as a marketable product. A full GTM analysis, including pricing, marketing & sales strategy and launch plan does not make sense at this time. However, identification of value propositions and target customers should be explored as a first step in a GTM.

8.2.1 Value Proposition

Our first step was to assess the potential benefit of AIDAVA for the healthcare market, with the support of the AIDAVA Sustainability Advisory Board (SAB) through several meetings and with in-depth conversation during a dedicated face to face workshop in October 2024. The results are detailed in *Deliverable 6.8. Recommendations from the Sustainability Advisory Board*; they led to two potential value propositions that are further explored below.

1. AIDAVA as enabler for interoperability of healthcare organisations in EHDS, supporting generation of EEHRxF based data exchange (and potentially other transformations)
2. AIDAVA as a social tool supporting patients—and delegated curators—to increase quality of data and therefore (digital) health equity & inclusion

Value proposition 1. AIDAVA as an interoperability enabler of EHDS

The context

At the heart of data management within the European Health Data Space (EHDS) are the data holders who collect personal data, including clinical data, social determinants of health and clinical research data. EHDS proposes the creation of different roles for public health authorities⁹, as displayed in the figure below.

⁹ These roles could be taken by existing organisations rather than creating de nove organisations across public health authorities. This should be decided in each country.

Figure 20. AIDAVA as an interoperability enabler of EHDS (3 areas) within Organisations and main information flows within proposed EHDS regulation.

Around clinical care:

1. National Contact Points for Digital Health (NCPDH) act as gateways for European citizens to access their data, pooled from data holders.
2. A Member State Digital Health Authority is responsible for enforcing the lawful use of data in health care delivery, certifying and supervising NCPDHs.
3. MyHealth@EU manages the infrastructure for cross-border management of health care delivery data.

Patients have the right to request data holders to access their data from this NCPDH; they will also benefit from having access to six priority categories of identifiable data in a standardised digital format they can share with healthcare providers throughout Europe to ensure safer unplanned care when travelling. These six categories include the International Patient Summary (IPS), lab report, ePrescription, eDispensation, Discharge Summary and Imaging reports; they are expected to be generated in a standardized format called the European exchange format (called EEHRxF [10]), compliant with HL7 FHIR. These six priority categories are expected to be provided by the relevant Data Holders, or rather by the vendors providing EHR systems the Data Holders.

Implementing acts are needed to clarify implementation and most specifically the following aspects.

- Who is responsible for an integrated IPS, when patients are being treated in different non communicating hospitals.
- How hospitals working with in-house proprietary EHR systems are expected to comply and generate these 6 priority categories. More precisely how are small remote/rural hospitals with less capacity and budget expected to find the budget and the needed skills to implement the EEHRxF standard. This needs to be addressed to avoid the risk of digital health inequity.
- Who will provide the additional budget needed to pay vendors for additional functionalities.

On the research and policymaking side:

1. Health Data Access Bodies (HDAB) are responsible for accessing and processing health data for secondary use for lawful purposes specified in the regulation.

2. A Coordinating Health Data Access Body enables cross-border secondary use of electronic health data under the responsibility of each Member State.
3. HealthData@EU managing the infrastructure for cross-border use of research and policymaking data.

Data users, defined as any natural or legal person who have lawful access to personal or non-personal electronic health data for secondary use, may submit a data access application to a HDAB for any purpose identified in the regulation. Patients who wish to understand how their personal health data are used, can access a public website.

While the regulation solves the issue related to access to data needed for public health (for instance in circumstances like epidemics), it does not solve the burden of recurrent curation. Health data are heterogeneous, multimodal data (medical imaging, genomic data, EHRs, wearables...) require different types of representation and technologies while, data standards for clinical care (HL7 FHIR, openEHR and clinical research (OMOP, CDISC) have different requirements. For the foreseeable future, health data curation will continue to be necessary i.e. expert data stewards will keep mapping and transforming heterogeneous data into the format required for the analysis. Data provided by each data holder are not linked and the curated data provides only a partial view of the patients. In addition, the number of subjects is often different from one data source to another. Finally, as each secondary use may require slightly different datasets, **one individual's data may be curated several times, resulting in massive and unnecessary duplication of effort.**

AIDAVA value proposition 1

As an interoperability enabler of EHDS, AIDAVA could support at 3 different levels, highlighted in Figure 20 and solving some of the issues mentioned above.

1. **Automatic generation of EEHRxF compliant data categories**
AIDAVA G1 can automatically generate IPS from the PHKG; this could easily be extended to the other 5 priority categories, provided the information is available in the data sources in scope of AIDAVA like system deployed in a data holder; this would alleviate the burden on hospitals and vendor to build HL7 skills & deliver EEHRxF. Deployment of AIDAVA in such hospitals - directly with the hospital or through the vendor - would not only help to increase the quality of their patient records but also ensure EHDS compliance.
2. **Automatic maintenance of patient population related information within the Data Description.** Per EHDS, each data holder has to maintain a Data Description which includes data elements related to Governance, Population Coverage, Data Quality Label and other Metadata. Currently the information related to patient population is limited to age range, number of records and description of the patient population in narrative format; this could be extended with structured information on the patient population, provided there is a mechanism to regularly update this information changing almost daily. From the PHKGs of all patients, AIDAVA can generate & maintain population related information for the organisation and should be able to automatically update this information in the Data Description. From the PHKGs across patients, AIDAVA could also generate & maintain a Data Quality Label of hospitals (when definitions are provided). Detailed population information and DQ label is extremely important to facilitate secondary data use. Without a tool like AIDAVA, maintenance of such information would be time consuming, and not done nor even envisioned currently.
3. **Support extraction - and exchange of information for secondary use.** AIDAVA could automatically generate high-quality datasets in any required format from the PHKG with relevant metadata, provided that all data sources available within the data holders have been

integrated and curated into the PHKG. This requires programming of SPARQL query to be executed on top of PHKGs. The same SPARQL query could be reused across all data holders supporting AIDAVA like PHKGs, de facto transforming a potentially heavy data extraction and curation process into running the same query across all organisations. The result of the SPARQL query - such as a CSV file - can be kept locally to maintain a local clinical registry, or can be transferred to an external location - provided that ethics, data privacy, security aspects have been correctly managed - to an outside organisation.

Value proposition 2. AIDAVA as social tool supporting increased quality of patient data and health equity & inclusion

The context

The painful reality about health data.

- Health data is *scattered* across multiple systems. Around 40% is managed and stored in one or more hospitals; 60% of health data is included in GP systems, home care, vaccination centers, dispensaries, clinical trials and increasingly in wearable devices.
- Health data is *heterogeneous*; it comes in a variety of formats and standards with different extensions and interpretations across borders.
- Health data is *not readily processable*. Up to 80% is in narrative format ($\pm 40\%$ in full narrative, $\pm 40\%$ in unstructured data with small chunks of text including acronyms and abbreviations)
- Health data is *not well documented*. Most health information systems in place in hospitals are old with ancient designs and technologies, with limited metadata and requirement on reuse.
- Health data is *redundant and error-prone*. Research indicates that up to 30% of information in a health record is redundant and can be the source of inconsistencies; up to 10% [11] patient records contain potentially life-threatening errors.
- *Assessing quality of health data* at source is not scalable. As individual patient data is heterogeneous and not computer processable, quality checks can only be implemented in a fragmented way and are too cumbersome to deploy.

As a consequence, health data is underused for prevention, treatment, research or public health decision making. This is not acceptable.

- It is not good enough for patients (and citizens) because their health records are disparate with questionable data quality; they are not sure they will receive appropriate quality of care.
- It is not good enough for frontline providers who do not have the time or tools needed to take an overall view of their patients' health. And they have to make decisions on the basis of fragmented and potentially incorrect data.
- It is not good enough for researchers and policy-makers. Because of the lack of interoperability of source data, they have to carry out tedious and recurrent curation of the source data.

Health organisations have limited capacity to improve health data quality: patients - and their deputy - can make a difference

While healthcare expenditure on average is 9.2% of GDP7 ($\pm 10\%$ in Europe, 17% in the US), the budget available for each individual health organisation to improve their legacy systems – and hire dedicated staff to increase the quality of data – is low. IT budgets within healthcare are still a low percentage,

between 2 to 5% as their core function is direct patient care, which involves staffing, medication, and medical equipment. IT plays a vital supporting role, but it's not the central focus of spending. Without profound changes in the healthcare system, *there does not seem much hope that quality of individual patient data will improve in the near future.*

This is where patients could make a difference, provided they are empowered with the appropriate infrastructure including the following components

- *Data intermediation services*, as regulated in the EU Data Governance Act Regulations [12] or by international frameworks such as the OECD Recommendation on Health Data Governance. Data intermediary services can be provided by public health authorities or potentially by private organisations. In AIDAVA, MIDATA is considered as a precursor of a Health Data Intermediary (HDI) organisation; its role was limited however to intermediation services of data. A full fledged data intermediary organisation would also need to have data processing rights supporting a set structured services as described in the MyData Operators Framework [13], following different business models [14]. HDI organisations can serve as trusted partners for patients to control the integration, curation and quality of their data, and to manage their preferences for sharing their data before it is reused in care delivery, research and policymaking.
- An *Intelligent Digital Assistant - like AIDAVA* - supporting patients to gather data across multiples sources and throughout their lifetime, transform this heterogeneous data in a high quality, interoperable and reusable longitudinal personal health record (PHR)
- Additional *intelligent agents* supporting providers and patients - and data users with patient consent - to use this high- quality FAIR PHR for decision support in clinical care and for policy-making and research purpose
- *Social Data Workers*, people specially trained in digital health and data management - like social service staff are trained in their discipline - that support patients and citizens not able to manage by themselves their health data and related digital health services. These social data workers would be reimbursed for their services in the same way as other social workers as they are increasingly important for health equity in an increasingly digital world.

AIDAVA value proposition 2

The second value proposition for AIDAVA - a social tool supporting patients and their delegated “social data workers” to increase the quality of their personal data and therefore (digital) health equity & inclusion - is one critical component of a patient centric EHDS infrastructure. If properly deployed it will enable a new paradigm in health data management and in EHDS.

- It is beneficial for patients and citizens as their record can be clean, accurate, complete, readily accessible by all (with their consent). If it is easy—hopefully seamless—for patients to manage and curate their data while benefiting from an integrated harmonised health record, they will be more likely to engage in managing their health data and in sharing them for the benefit of the population, and ultimately in managing their personal health.
- It is beneficial for frontline providers as the Intelligent Digital Assistant helps them to acquire a comprehensive view of the patient with limited effort.
- It is beneficial for researchers and policy-makers; when they need data they can request different data intermediaries organisations who will manage consent of the patients they serve and provide data in the format needed; there is no need to manage consent, there is no need to curate the data.

8.2.1 Target Markets

The first question to ask when developing a product is to identify if this should focus on a mass market (as wide an audience as possible) or a target market with specific needs. While centred around the patient/citizens, AIDAVA is a product aiming to solve data interoperability and data quality issues i.e a very specialised topic **which points to a targeted approach**, for the following reasons.

- The audience for this type of software is likely to be relatively small and specialised, i.e. organisations managing data (on behalf of, with and for the patient like Health Data Intermediaries (HDI), though not necessarily limited to this). Attempting to market the software to a mass market would result in a lot of wasted effort and resources, as the majority of the general population would not understand the value of the software, without additional training and services.
- A targeted approach allows for more precise targeting of marketing channels that are most likely to be effective for the specific audience. For example, if the audience is primarily made up of professionals in a particular public health domain or in the hospital sector, targeting industry-specific conferences or trade publications would likely be more effective than generic advertising channels. In addition, if successful, the approach developed in AIDAVA could be applied – against target customers – in other sectors, not directly related to healthcare, and we could more easily reach these other sectors through a targeted approach.
- Focusing on a targeted approach can also help to establish the software as a specialised and highly valuable solution within the industry. This can help to differentiate the software from other generic solutions on data quality enhancement and position it as the go-to solution for organisations looking to enhance their data quality and interoperability.

Potential target customers

The AIDAVA virtual assistant should be of interest to stakeholders who need to integrate and curate heterogenous personal health data (PHD) and want to reuse this data for different purposes in clinical care as well as in clinical research.

- **Hospitals** running a Hospital Information System composed of multiple different, often non integrated systems, across departments. They would benefit from deploying and running a system like AIDAVA to integrate and curate data coming from these different systems at different levels.
- **Software vendors** that serve healthcare organisations, and mainly EHR vendors are expected to provide additional functionalities as part of the EHDS deployments (see Chapter III of the regulation); this includes documentation, data quality labels and provision of additional functionalities such as the generation of the 6 critical data categories in EEHRx format.
- **(Regional) Public Health services serving as "Patient Hub" or National Contact Points for Digital Health (NCPDH)** introduced in the EHDS – and building on infrastructure already in place in several EU countries (e.g. Health Data Hub in France, eHealth.gov in Belgium, HELGA in Austria, TEHIK in Estonia,..) – are centralising health data from individuals, across multiple data sources, including healthcare organisations such as hospitals, GPs, nursing homes, vaccination centres but also research infrastructure such as biobanks/genome DBs, and clinical trial data databases, and increasingly data collected through personal apps and medical devices.

- **Health Data Access Bodies (HDAB)** responsible for processing health data for secondary use on the basis of the conditions specified in the regulation, including access to identifiable data conditioned to the availability of a Permit. They extract data from Data Holders and process them to make them ready for analysis.
- As identified during the AIDAVA use cases analysis, **Health Data Intermediaries (HDI)** are emerging actors supporting the patients in managing and controlling their data. In the context of the prototype, it was decided – for security, data privacy issues and ethical consideration – that the prototype managing sensitive personal data will function only within the Hospital environment to avoid that any data collected by Healthcare providers would leave the hospital. In the long run however, we envision that AIDAVA might run within HDI—public or privately owned—so that patients can truly manage and curate, if needed, all their personal health data from different sources through a single actor.
- **Pharmaceutical companies** (or the **Clinical Research Organisations** supporting them) are also Data Holders of data collected during clinical trials.

Value proposition & target market maturity assessment

	1. Interoperability enabler of EHDS			2. Social tool supporting increased quality of patient data and health equity & inclusion through integrated dossier
	1.1. Automatic generation of EEHRxF	1.2. Maintenance of population information in Data Description	1.3. Extraction & exchange of information for secondary use	
Hospitals	+++	<i>(++) conditional to regulation</i>	+++	++
SW vendors				? (low maturity)
Public Health as “patient hub”	<i>Only if taking the role of “public” Health Data Intermediaries - with complete “pool” of data</i>			+
Health Data Hub	-	<i>(+) as consumer conditional to regulation</i>	+++	-
Health Data intermediaries	+++ <i>(low maturity)</i>	+++ <i>(low maturity)</i>	+++ <i>(low maturity)</i>	+++ <i>(low maturity)</i>
Research Organisations	-	<i>(+++ as consumer conditional to regulation</i>	+++	-

Hospitals

They are probably the organisations that would benefit the most from AIDAVA; they could deploy AIDAVA directly with their own IT department or benefit from it through their vendors.

VP1.1. Transformation and transfer in HL7 FHIR (e.g. IPS) to meet regulatory requirements (in alignment with EHDS) and ensure continuity of care across borders is probably the most important value for Hospital

VP1.2. Maintenance of detailed population information, if enforced by extending the Data Description being deployed as part of the EHDS would be a second important asset of AIDAVA. Detailed patient population information would allow hospitals to monetize their data more easily. For-profit data users - such as pharmaceutical companies - are looking for that kind of information to identify the most appropriate hospitals with which to collaborate on clinical trials, whether they are observational trials with extraction of existing data to generate clinical registries, or interventional trials with patient recruitment.

VP1.3. Hospitals have to deliver multiple data sets to different stakeholders, in different formats.

- Internal Clinical registries for clinical research. With a hospital, it is frequent that different departments maintain different therapeutic areas specific registries for clinical research. Different scientific staff (nurses, medical students, junior physicians) with different skill sets curate—most often manually—the same data of the same patient, multiple times, often with inconsistencies and suboptimal quality.
- Hospitals have a legal obligation to transfer data regularly to regional/national healthcare authorities such as National Contact Points for Digital Health (NCPDH) as described before but also to reimbursement organisations.
- Transfer to research organisation/ pharmaceutical companies in CDISC format as part of clinical trial (electronic data capture) or in OMOP format to support development of so-called "real world data sets".

In short, hospitals regularly need to extract and transfer - or reuse locally - patient data that are most often scattered across multiple subsystems. With AIDAVA, data from the patients will be first pooled across the different subsystems and then curated once and only once; data relevant for a specific purpose (registry, national obligations & reimbursement, clinical trials) can automatically be extracted and transformed into the required format .

Figure 21. Moving away from time consuming specific data extraction
To 1/2 automated extracts.

VP2. By providing to their own physician a **fully integrated dossier of the patient**, hospitals would ensure high quality of medical decision making and higher quality of care thanks to better and more easily accessible data. Currently physicians have to look across systems to build a view of their patient. This can be time consuming and increases the burden of already overloaded clinical staff. With AIDAVA, hospitals would benefit from a fully integrated longitudinal health record; this assumes the availability of “social data workers” - potentially reimbursed for their work - to maintain the dossiers of the patient who are not able/willing to curate and maintain their own dossier. Additional tools - AI and non-AI - would need to be developed to support intelligent navigation in this dossier.

Software vendors.

As service providers for data holders, SW vendors would benefit in the same way as the hospitals from the VP1 related value propositions of AIDAVA around interoperability enablement of EHDS. Their interest in VP2 is however less clear: this is a new market for public health services and therefore with unclear financial size and unknown questions around the roles, responsibility and financing of organisations providing data intermediation services. This will be further discussed within *Deliverable 4.12 Proposed operating model for HDI*, due in August 2026

"Patient Hub" or National Contact Points for Digital Health (NCPDH)

These are new organisations - or rather new functions within existing public health organisations - introduced in the EHDS, responsible for "pooling" all patient data in such a central hub.

In the EHDS, their role is limited to pooling the data and giving access to these data to the patients and to the providers. There is no clear provision for additional processing of these data such as curation and quality enhancement to increase the interoperability and reusability of these data in clinical care (“primary use” setting).

In the current context, there is therefore a limit value for AIDAVA in NCDPHs. This could change dramatically if NCDPH would become “public” health data intermediaries as described below.

Health Data Access Bodies (HDAB)

By definition of their roles in EHDS, HDAB will have to spend time curating information from multiple different data holders. Even if they may get a “standard” syntactical format they define when mandating data extraction, they cannot mandate data quality and semantic interoperability which will remain low and requires manual curation and quality check. Configuring and deploying AIDAVA could drastically reduce the time spent in such effort.

In addition, HDAB would benefit from Data Description of Data Holders complemented with detailed population information: whenever HDAB needed to extract information from targeted patient population - rather than complete population - they could more effectively contact the Data Holders with patient population of interest.

Health Data Intermediaries (HDI)

As identified during the use cases analysis, **Health Data Intermediaries (HDI)** are emerging actors supporting the patients in managing and controlling their data. In the following way

- Provide better direct services to their patients, including tools supporting visualisation of the health record based on integrated longitudinal data.
- Provide new services to their patients, allowing them to value their data for the common good, by sharing these data for clinical research of public interest, but also enabling the patient to share their data with commercial organisations—like pharma companies—and receive some benefit out of their data.

JRC [14] introduced six types of data intermediaries' business models. This will be further extended in D4.12. In the context of the EHDs We could envision two types of HDI.

- **Publicly run** i.e. equivalent to the NCDPH mentioned above; this would typically be the case in patient/population centric healthcare systems such as Spain and Finland. Deployment of AIDAVA should be more effective in these countries - as organisational and ethical hurdles should be less complex thanks to centralization.
- **Privately owned** and responsible for pooling - with express patient consent - all patient data gathered across multiples data sources; this would typically be the case in hospital centric healthcare systems with very strict data protection laws such as in Germany where patient can only have access to PDF based information (even if the source data are in a structured). Thanks to constantly improving capabilities around OCR and NLP tools, managing paper-based data sources is becoming a non-issue. Ethical constraints and management of patient consent needed to integrate data from many data sourced and to curate these data will remain hard across a wide population; it could be addressed with emerging dynamic consent management solutions piloted in EU for travel¹⁰.

Even though this is a low maturity market, AIDAVA would be of tremendous value for all value propositions identified above.

Research Organisations

Pharmaceutical companies (or the **Clinical Research Organisations** supporting them) benefit from the AIDAVA at 2 levels

VP1.2. Having access to detailed population information in the Data Description of the different Data Holders/hospitals would be of major value for the clinical research organisations who need to execute clinical trials. Currently they maintain - mostly manually and with large teams - site information with the type of patient population and availability of skilled resources to support trials. This is time and money consuming and very difficult to maintain across the 15.000+ European hospitals. As a consequence, assessment of clinical trial feasibility - before recruitment - remains a tedious process often prone to errors that leads to subrecruitment, delays or even failures in clinical trials execution. A well documented and properly maintain Data Description would maintain data privacy of patients and providers and could bring drastic improvements in the clinical trials assessment process

VP1.3. Extraction & exchange of information for secondary use and development of real world clinical registries is increasingly important for clinical research organisations (pharma and CRO) to optimise clinical trial execution. Currently they execute this on a case by case, as the HDAB, extracting and curating data from multiple data holders. Configuring and deploying AIDAVA could drastically reduce the time spent in such curation.

¹⁰ See <https://eudiwalletconsortium.org/>

9. References

- [1] “[No title].” Accessed: Apr. 29, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://zenodo.org/records/10117718/files/AIDAVA_101057062_D2.1_Global%20Data%20Sharing%20Standard_final_zenodo.pdf?download=1
- [2] I. De Zegher *et al.*, “D1.1 Description of use cases”, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10075525.
- [3] I. De Zegher, R. Çelebi, L. Powell, B. Bihari, and D. Dallos, “D2.3 Solution Design Document for G1”, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10245773.
- [4] M. Kargl, “D1.3 Business requirements for G1”, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10075580.
- [5] “Website.” [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52021PC0206>
- [6] “Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT) - Version 3.” Accessed: Apr. 29, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>
- [7] “Public consultations,” Tehdas. Accessed: Apr. 29, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://tehdas.eu/public-consultations/>
- [8] “Large Language Models in Healthcare and Medical Domain: A Review.” Accessed: Oct. 17, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/html/2401.06775v2>
- [9] “Website.” [Online]. Available: <https://www.archimatetool.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/c4-overview.png>
- [10] “Recommendation on a European Electronic Health Record exchange format,” Shaping Europe’s digital future. Accessed: Apr. 29, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/recommendation-european-electronic-health-record-exchange-format>
- [11] S. K. Bell *et al.*, “Frequency and Types of Patient-Reported Errors in Electronic Health Record Ambulatory Care Notes,” *JAMA Netw Open*, vol. 3, no. 6, p. e205867, Jun. 2020, doi: 10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2020.5867.
- [12] “Website.” [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32022R0868>
- [13] “Understanding MyData Operators.” Accessed: Apr. 29, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://mydata.org/publication/understanding-mydata-operators/>
- [14] M. Micheli, E. Farrell, S. B. Carballa, S. M. Posada, S. Signorelli, and M. Vespe, *Mapping the landscape of data intermediaries*. 2023. doi: 10.2760/261724.
- [15] I. de Zegher *et al.*, “Artificial intelligence based data curation: enabling a patient-centric European health data space,” *Front. Med.*, vol. 11, p. 1365501, May 2024, doi: 10.3389/fmed.2024.1365501.
- [16] “Home.” Accessed: Feb. 08, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.aidava.eu/>

10. Annexes

A.1 Template of integration & testing specifications

The template provided below was used to define the integration specification of most of the components of AIDAVA adapted for G2 ([link](#))

- NLP
- Entity Linking
- Entity Deduplication
- Imaging
- Publishing of data elements for FHIR IPS
- Publishing of data elements of the BC registry
- Publishing of data elements to compute the CVD score

Call: HORIZON-HLTH-2021-TOOL-06

Topic: HORIZON-HLTH-2021-TOOL-06-03

Funding Scheme: HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions (RIA)

Grant Agreement no: 101057062

AI powered Data Curation & Publishing Virtual Assistant

**TEMPLATE: INTEGRATION
Specifications and Testing of
<integration_component>**

Date: dd/mm/20205

Responsible partner: ????

Grant agreement no.

101057062

Project full title	AIDAVA—AI powered Data Curation & Publishing Virtual Assistant
---------------------------	--

Deliverable number	Not relevant (internal use)
Deliverable title	Not relevant (internal use)
Type ¹¹	R
Dissemination level ¹²	SEN
Work package number	WP3
Work package leader	P8—GND
Author(s)	
Reviewers	Isabelle de Zegher (P2-b!loba) Remzi Celebi (P1—UM) Bela Bihari and Daniel Dallos (P8—GND)
Keywords	

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA). The work of MID received funding by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SBFI), subvention contract 22.00093, REF-1131-52104.

Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Document History

Version	Date	Description
V0.1		
V1		
V2		

¹¹ **Type:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action):

R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

¹² **Dissemination level:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action)

PU: Public, fully open, e.g. web
SEN: Sensitive, limited under conditions of the Grant Agreement

Table of Contents

Foreword	4
1. Description/specification of the component	5
Summary	5
1.1 Scope	5
1.2 Requirements	5
1.3 Assumptions related to implementation	5
1.4 Method	6
1.5 Link to implementation	6
2. Design and architecture including data flows	7
2.1 Architecture and data flows	7
2.2. Input and Output description	7
2.3. Integration & deployment requirement (e.g. SW/HW,..)	7
3. For AI (machine learning and generative AI component)	8
3.1 Input data used to train the model	8
3.2 Human oversights	8
3.3. Performance metrics	8
3.4 Capabilities and limitations in performance	8
3.5 Potential risks—including unintended outcomes	8
4. Validation and testing	9
4.1 Description of approach/strategy	9
4.2 Unit/module testing	9
4.3. Integration testing	9
Annexes	10
1. Annex IV of the AI Act (Technical Documentation)	10

Foreword

This document is a template of the documentation to be delivered for each component to be integrated in the backend of the AIDAVA prototype.

This documentation is required for the following reasons.

- Operational
 - Specifications— including scope, requirements, assumptions, input and output—are needed to ensure that all parties share the same understanding.
 - Testing—including description of approach, description of testing data and/or how they will be gathered and made accessible, and result of testing execution—is critically important to ensure that the component to be integrated works properly before it is actually integrated with the overall application
 - Any specific integration requirement
- Regulatory compliance: per the [AI Act](#), approved in May 2024. The regulation applies to high-risk AI systems tested in real world conditions: AI is a high-risk AI system and G2 of the prototype will be tested with real patients on site.

The EU AI Act enters into force across all 27 EU Member States on 1 August 2024, and the enforcement of the majority of its provisions will commence on 2 August 2026. As G2 will be tested early 2026, enforcement should not apply to AIDAVA, but reviewers may require information.

The AI Act requires that the high-risks AI system—as a WHOLE—includes detailed technical documentation (Annex IV of the regulation). Out of this, we extracted a set of information that we estimate should be included in the description of each component (see Annex 1 in this document).

- *Description/specification of the component including*
 - *Scope—and related curation workflow if applicable*
 - *Known business requirements,*
 - *Assumptions related to implementation*
 - *Method (AI or other; if AI, describe type of approach and algorithm)*
- *Design and architecture including data flows including*
 - *input and output description (content, format)*
 - *specific integration requirement (e.g. SW/HW...)*
- *For AI—machine learning and generative AI component*
 - *Input data used to train the model*
 - *Human oversights, including the technical measures put in place to facilitate the interpretation of the outputs of AI systems by the deployers;*
 - *Performance metrics: definition, why they are appropriate, how to measure,*
 - *Capabilities and limitations in performance*
 - *Potential risks—including unintended outcomes—to be included in the risk management system of the complete system*
- *Validation and testing including*
 - *description of approach/strategy,*
 - *description of testing data and/or how they will be gathered and made accessible,*
 - *result of testing*

1. Description/specification of the component

Summary

The following information will be used in the explainability module of the AIDAVA G2 app for patients.

Name of the component:	
Version of the component:	
Task of the component: <i>Brief description of the task of this component during AIDAVA's curation workflow. Important: use lay language!</i>	
Technology used: <i>example: natural language processing (NLP), a machine learning technology that enables computers to recognise and understand text</i>	
Manufacturer: <i>Name of the Institution + Country</i>	

1.1 Scope

Includes background information

1.2 Requirements

- List of requirements that were identified by the business/development team
- Automation requirements with related curation workflow if applicable

1.3 Assumptions related to implementation

...any assumption on the implementation and integration

1.4 Method

- (AI or other; if AI, describe type of approach and algorithm)
- Includes reference to existing/published work if relevant

1.5 Link to implementation

- Github reference
- Specification of code

2. Design and architecture including data flows

2.1 Architecture and data flows

Provide a schema —whenever relevant link to relevant workflow from Deliverable D2.2

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1IH1UaeiL4hnOJ34u3WfKMbstj4CwLsYNlc4Byhp_Pk8/edit

2.2. Input and Output description

(description, content, format)

2.3. Integration & deployment requirement (e.g. SW/HW...)

Specifically important is GPU is required

3. For AI (machine learning and generative AI component)

3.1 Input data used to train the model

- type of data
- where they are coming from
- any issues related to data privacy (including need for EC approval to access)

3.2 Human oversights

including the technical measures put in place to facilitate the interpretation of the outputs of AI systems by the deployers.

3.3. Performance metrics

- Definition of the metrics and why they are appropriate, meaning of results
- How to measure (and needed information to be captured to measure)

Note: accuracy and precision is good but are they powerful enough to truly measure effectiveness and reliability in real life .. If we have anything below 100% accuracy and precision, does this mean we cannot use the tool in real life ?? We know the 100% are not realistic, so what do we do ? We might need to link the level of performance with human oversight/ risk management.. quite an interesting topic .

3.4 Capabilities and limitations in performance

3.5 Potential risks—including unintended outcomes

List of risks that could happen and that should be checked with the complete system and to be included in the risk management system of the complete system

4. Validation and testing

4.1 Description of approach/strategy

Testing will take place in different steps

- Unit & module testing (functional level, each module on an isolated environment):
 - Unit testing—make sure specific function of the component works
 - Module testing—make sure that the component as a whole works as expected.
- Responsibility of the provider of the tool

- Integration testing (interactions between different integrated components) —covered by GND
- Regression testing (tests ensuring that changes don't break the system; improves the process of finding issues in complex use cases)—covered by GND

4.2 Unit/module testing

4.2.1 Test data

4.2.2 Results of testing

.....

4.3. Integration testing

What needs to be tested:

- ...

4.3.1 Test data

4.3.2 Results of testing

Annexes

1. Annex IV of the AI Act (Technical Documentation)

The text below is extracted from the AI Act

- General description
- Detailed description of the elements of the AI system and of the process for its development: methods, design, architecture, data, human oversights, validation and testing procedures, cybersecurity
- Detailed information about
 - monitoring, functioning and control of the AI system (capabilities and limitations in performance; the foreseeable unintended outcomes and sources of risks),
 - human oversight measures needed in accordance with Article 14, including the technical measures put in place to facilitate the interpretation of the outputs of AI systems by the deployers;
 - specifications on input data, as appropriate;
- Description of the appropriateness of the performance metrics
- Detailed description of the risk management system in accordance with Article 9;
- Description of relevant changes made by the provider to the system through its lifecycle;
- List of the harmonised standards applied in full or in part the references of which have been published in the Official Journal of the European Union; where no such harmonised standards have been applied, a detailed description of the solutions adopted to meet the requirements set out in Chapter III, Section 2;
- Copy of the EU declaration of conformity referred to in Article 47;
- Detailed description of the system in place to evaluate the AI system performance in the post-market phase in accordance with Article 72, including the post-market monitoring plan referred to in Article 72(3).

Based on this, we suggest including the following information in the documentation of each individual component of the AIDAVA prototype which is based on AI methodology.

- Description of the component
- Method used (type of algorithm)
- Design and architecture including specification on input data
- Capabilities and limitations in performance
- Human oversights, including the technical measures put in place to facilitate the interpretation of the outputs of AI systems by the deployers;
- Performance metrics: definition, why they are appropriate, how to measure,
- Potential risks—including unintended outcomes—to be included in the risk management system of the complete system
- Validation and testing procedures,
- Out of scope for AIDAVA but relevant to add for a full fledge product
 - Cybersecurity
 - Description of changes made through its lifecycle;
 - List of the harmonised standards applied or a detailed description of the solutions adopted to meet the requirements set out in Chapter III, Section 2;

- Aspects to be included in the post-market monitoring plan for the complete system

A.2 Recommendations for deployment of AIDAVA outside of project

Call: HORIZON-HLTH-2021-TOOL-06

Topic: HORIZON-HLTH-2021-TOOL-06-03

Funding Scheme: HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions (RIA)

Grant Agreement no: 101057062

AI powered Data Curation & Publishing Virtual Assistant

**Annex to D2.4. Solution Design.
Deployment approach of AIDAVA G2
prototype
Description, benefits, limitations and work plan**

Date: February 2025

Responsible partner: P2—b!lo, P1—UM,

Grant agreement no.	101057062
Project full title	AIDAVA—AI powered Data Curation & Publishing Virtual Assistant

Deliverable number	Internal document for communication with external partners interested in deploying G2 prototype of AIDAVA
Deliverable title	Report of G1 Performance
Type ¹³	R
Dissemination level ¹⁴	SEN (external distribution on request)
Work package number	WP6
Work package leader	P8—NEMC and P2—b!loba
Author(s)	Isabelle de Zegher, P2 – b!loba Remzi Celebi, P1—UM Daniel Dallos, P9- GND Kris Collins, P10—AVER Dipak Kalra, P6—IHD Kristof Vanfraechem, P12—DFP Dominik Steiger, Emmanuel Benoist, P13—MID
Keywords	

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The work of MID received funding by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SBFI), subvention contract 22.00093, REF-1131-52104.

Supported by a licence waiver from SNOMED International from a period of 2 years (2024 – 2025), on condition that SNOMED CT is not used and/or deployed commercially.

Document History

Version	Date	Description
V0.1	9 February 2025	Initial version for review by relevant AIDAVA partners
V1.0		Final version ready for controlled distribution to external partners

¹³ **Type:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action):

R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

¹⁴ **Dissemination level:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action)

PU: Public, fully open, e.g. web
SEN: Sensitive, limited under conditions of the Grant Agreement

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	4
1 Introduction to the AIDAVA G2 prototype	5
1.1 Objectives of AIDAVA	5
1.2 High level architecture	6
1.3 Evaluation of Generation 1 (G1): July to December 2024	7
1.4 Evaluation of Generation 2 (G2): December 2025 to March 2026	7
2 Benefits, Challenges and limitations of the AIDAVA prototype	8
2.1 Benefits	8
2.2 Limitations	9
3 Deploying AIDAVA: needed steps	10
3.1 Preparation (before deployment)	10
3.2 Development	11
3.3 Deployment	13
4 References	13
Annexes.	14
Annex 1. Infrastructure requirement	14
Assumptions	14
Needed infrastructure	14
Assumptions	15
Needed infrastructure	15
FAQ	15
Annex 2. Customer Support	16
Annex 3. List of project deliverables	18

List of Definitions

The definitions used in the deliverable are based on the AIDAVA Glossary [[ref](#)].

List of Abbreviations

Executive Summary

This document is intended for any health care organisation (hospital, national authorities, ..) that wants/needs to transform its data—typically in heterogeneous format and narrative text—into an interoperable format, for reuse in the context of care (like FHIR), research (like OMOP or CDISC) public health or policy-making.

The document first introduces the AIDAVA prototype: its objective, main components and status. It then describes its benefits as well as its limitations. The last section provides a detailed list of the steps needed for the deployment of the AIDAVA prototype, and potential support services during execution.

AIDAVA has a well defined scope and limited budget. While the coordinating team is happy to explore potential deployment, final agreement is subject to availability of additional funding and appropriate resources within the consortium. Additional funding could be provided from supporting programs from the European Commission such as European Innovation Council (EIC) Work Programme 2025¹⁵

¹⁵ See page 8 in https://eic.ec.europa.eu/document/download/5e1eb75f-e437-477f-9ee9-ef54ff6387fd_en

1 Introduction to the AIDAVA G2 prototype

AIDAVA prototype [15] results from the AIDAVA Horizon Europe project [16], under Grant Agreement #101057062. The project started in September 2022 and will end in August 2026.

The prototype is an intelligent virtual assistant (VA) intended to be used by patients, or their delegate, and a specialised data curator and assist them in curating their heterogeneous, multimodal, personal health data into an interoperable and reusable Personal Health Knowledge Graph (PHKG). This PHKG constitutes de facto the patient longitudinal health record that is regularly updated as new data sources become available.

Individuals' PHKGs, taken alone or grouped across a population, can be transformed into multiple formats for reuse and sharing in clinical care context, in clinical research or in public health and policy making.

1.1 Objectives of AIDAVA

The AIDAVA prototype aims to maximise automation of the curation process by orchestrating the execution of complementary AI and non-AI based curation tools according to the data interoperability issue found in a data source. When automated curation is not achievable, the VA initiates a dialogue with the patient or data curator, based on their preferences and skill levels, starting with a question supported by adaptive explanations.

The AIDAVA VA generates two types of results from the patient's PHKG:

1. fully identifiable data extracted from a single patient's PHKG, in the form of the patient's cardiovascular risk score and International Patient Summary (IPS) in HL7 FHIR format compliant with the EHDS EEHRxF format
2. anonymized population datasets extracted from multiple PHKGs to form an interoperable, site-specific breast cancer clinical registry that can be federated with other sites.

These constitute examples of potential outputs implemented during the project; many other outputs are possible building on the semantic richness and reusability of the PHKG.

1.2 High level architecture

Figure 1. Overview of the AIDAVA Virtual Assistant

The AIDAVA prototype VA is composed of a backend and a frontend.

The **backend** includes foundational components to maximize the potential of automation during the curation process. This comprises among others

- a **catalogue of data sources** with metadata describing the data sources and supporting mapping and linkage with the specific curation & publishing workflows at the basis of automation;
- a **library of curation tools** including 17+ data curation and publishing tools used in the workflows
 - non-AI tools: ETL/ Extract Transformation Load from FHIR or DICOM to RDF, SHACL checks, ..
 - AI-based tools: Optical Recognition Character (OCR), Machine Based Translation, Natural Language Processing(NLP), Entity Linking (EL),...
 - publishing tools: generation of IPS in FHIR format from the PHKG available RDF format, extract of data elements from the PHKG and transformation in OMOP like format..

Execution of the different workflows and related tools is done through an orchestration workflow based on the type of data interoperability to be solved in a data source (e.g. narrative text requires NLP, small snip of text requires Entity Linking,..)

- the **reference ontology** which is the standard of reference for each PHKG to which all data sources are transformed;
- the **repository of patient data** – raw data, PHKG and published data in the target standard;
- the **orchestration module** that supports automation and interaction with the end users.

The **frontend** interacts with users, sending questions to the patient or data curator based on the level of complexity of a question and the health and digital literacy level of the patient. Questions are linked with tailored explanations to facilitate understanding of the questions.

To ensure a true patient-centred approach, the project is supported by eight patient 'consultants' from the European Heart Network for Cardiovascular Diseases and DataForPatient organisation. These patient consultants are actively involved at regular, well-defined times throughout the project, to ensure the project stays focused on what is important for patients. In addition, the team collected end-user feedback through a survey which received over 250+ replies and study nurses collected a lot of patient feedback during enrollment and participation in the assessment of Generation 1 .

The AIDAVA prototype is developed through 2 generations. The objective for Generation 1 (G1) was to focus on the front end, to test acceptance by the patients and their supporting curators, while the curation tools in the backend are based on existing tools. The focus on Generation 2 (G2) is to improve

the back end curation tools to increase the amount of automation and minimize the need for user interactions. with the front end prototype.

1.3 Evaluation of Generation 1 (G1): July to December 2024

G1 was deployed and tested within 4 clinical sites (Maastricht University Medical Center and Maastricht Clinic in the Netherlands, Sihtasutus Pohja-Eesti Regionaalhaigla in Estonia, Medizinische Universität Graz in Austria) with the support of MIDATA Genossenschaft data intermediary organisation in Estonia and Austria. The evaluation lasted 6 months, from July to December 2024.

Thirty eighth (38) Cardiovascular patients admitted for myocardial infarction and forty five (45) Breast Cancer patients participated in the evaluation, following a structured protocol approved by the local ethics committee. The overall performance was—as expected— suboptimal. It raised concerns from the patients' perspective (e.g., unclear and burdensome questions raised by the system, lack of direct benefits) and from the data users (e.g., lack of usable high-quality data to support). The acceptance of this first prototype by the users was slightly above medium: the patients perceived the importance and value of the prototype while realizing that it was only a first step in what should be ultimately deployed. They mainly expected to have a clearer interaction with the system in case of questions during the curation process. In addition the evaluation was extremely useful for the project teams: the site study teams learned how to configure the system and how to run the evaluation process, the development team crystallised several technical issues to be solved or improved for G2.

The G1 prototype confirmed there is true potential—and interest by patients— in automated data curation of health data into a harmonised semantic standard, under the form of a Personal Health Knowledge Graph.

1.4 Evaluation of Generation 2 (G2): December 2025 to March 2026

The objective of G2 to be deployed in December 2025 is focus on improving the data curation tools running in the backend to maximize automation, while minimizing the amount of questions for the patients and curators, therefore decreasing the burden on them.

2 Benefits, Challenges and limitations of the AIDAVA prototype

AIDAVA Virtual Assistant (VA) is a prototype, not a product. It has benefits as well as limitations.

2.1 Benefits

AIDAVA has 2 foundational benefits.

- **Toward a solution of lack of interoperability of health data.** AIDAVA VA demonstrates that data interoperability, a long standing problem, can be greatly simplified (and potentially solved) by orchestrating different AI and non AI tools tackling specific data interoperability issues¹⁶ in the different data sources.
- **Introduce a paradigm shift in health data management,** from “*curate many times, use once*” to the “*curate once, use many times*”. AIDAVA focuses on the curation of the foundational data in health care i.e. the patient health record, and reuse this curated patient record (the PHKG) many times. By focusing on the patient record first, it is possible to maximise its quality and provide well needed longitudinal data to the providers. In addition, extraction of data from this high quality, reusable record, and transformation into specific format for research or public health can be largely automated, avoiding time consuming recurrent curation.

This concretely translated into direct benefits for organisations and patients

- Organisations who need to maintain a real world/clinical data registry and today require workload intensive semi-manual curation of heterogeneous data sources coming from multiples centers can use AIDAVA to maximize automation in curation and relieve much of the workload while increasing the quality and interoperability, by suppressing differences in mapping across curators, of the resulting data sets.
- Patients who start to have access to health data intermediaries, managing their data and the consent to share these data will have the possibility to use AIDAVA—deployed within their health data intermediaries—to increase the quality of their own personal health record. This may in turn help them—and their providers—to have access to more personalized care and potentially to more clinical trials as their eligibility criteria for specific trials can be more easily checked.

In addition, any product derived from AIDAVA would be a key component for effective and cost-saving implementation of interoperability within the EHDS. From a complete, high quality PHKG,

- each patient could extract the 6 primary data categories mandated by EHDS (article 5) in EEHRxF first (article 6);
- EHR providers could derive the needed specifications (article 23)
- HDAB would have more readily usable and higher quality data (article 33) for secondary use

2.2 Limitations

As AIDAVA VA is a prototype, it comes with inherent limitations.

- The prototype is based on the AIDAVA reference ontology derived from the Swiss SPHN schema. To ensure semantic consistency and smooth mapping across any type of data source

¹⁶ Interoperability issues include: paper format, unstructured narratives, semi-structured data with snippets of text and structured data, structured data with specific format & terminology requiring alignment, metadata related to imaging, missing information, errors and inconsistencies across data sources.

and output format, this ontology needs alignment with other standards (from clinical care like FHIR, SNOMED, LOINC, openEHR .. and clinical research like OMOP, CDISC, MEDDRA, ICH, ...) through a **semantic interoperability standard** in the form of an upper level ontology agreed across all parties. AIDAVA has initiated the development of a “**Simplified Upper Level Ontology**” and will organize consensus meetings to ensure wider acceptance and use.

- The prototype is available in German, Estonia and Dutch¹⁷. Any **new language** requires translation of the user interface in this language and development of new AI tools to extract structured data from narrative text (NLP) or snip of text (Entity Linking).
- The prototype provides a Data Quality label for the Personal Health Knowledge Graph (PHKG) with indication on consistency, volume, and availability of context information. This label is however not sufficient to secure trust of providers on data users on the clinical usability of the PHKG. We need to develop—or reuse— a **clinical usability and quality assessment mechanism** to ensure that any output from AIDAVA is linked with a clinical trust score that represents its clinical usability that can be checked with providers and other data users.
- **Compliance with the AI Act and MDR** will be required as of August 2026 as AIDAVA is managing personal health data and should therefore be considered as a high-risk AI system.

¹⁷ English could be made available but would require retraining of the existing NLP model and validation of the already developed user interface.

3 Deploying AIDAVA: needed steps

This section describes the different steps needed to deploy the AIDAVA prototype as such. We do not advise to deploy G1. While the G2 prototype itself will be available and fully tested only by the end of November 2025, several steps must be undertaken before it is deployed.

The table below provides an overview of the work to be done to deploy G2 with the current functionalities; exact estimates can be provided when the use case is clarified

	Months												Estimated Workload (PM=person months)		
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	Site	AIDAVA	
Preparation															
Use case definition	■	■	■	■											b!lo/DFP: ±20 days
Data Transfer Specifications		■	■	■	■	■									UM: 5 - 20 days
Ethical Committee approval to request possibility to process personal, identifiable data															
Preparation & submission protocol	■	■	■	■	■	■									IHD: ± 10 days
Data Privacy/ DPO approval		■	■	■	■	■									
Follow up with updates as needed		■	■	■	■	■									
Development & testing (can be shortened if Therapeutic Area and language already available)															
SetUp test environment			■	■											GND: ?
Ontology update				■	■	■									UM/AVER: ?
Additional DQ checks					■	■	■	■							UM: 6 PM
Data Extract from source						■	■								UM: 6 PM
Mapping					■	■									UM: 3 PM
Front end translation						■	■								GND: ?
Translation of MIDATA HDI					■	■									MID: ± 20 KEUR
Integration MIDATA					■	■									MID: ± 30 KEUR
NLP - other language			■	■	■	■	■								AVER: ?
Entity Linking			■	■	■	■	■								AVER/UM/ONTO: ?
Output generation (SPARQL)							■	■							UM: 3 PM
Deployment & execution															
Tool deployment											■				GND: ?
Training											■	■			b!lo/DFP:
Execution with customer support & publishing												■	■		GND
Use of published output												■	■		-
TOTAL WORKLOAD															

Table 1. Proposed Deployment plan for AIDAVA - exact workload to be agreed with external partners.

Color code: orange = must do task; green = needed if TA is different;

cyan = needed if MIDATA HDI is needed for non hospital data; grey = needed if language is different

3.1 Preparation (before deployment)

3.1.1 Use case and identification of missing components

The first step is to clarify the use case and the (data interoperability) problem to be solved

- What is the therapeutic area in scope
- What are the data sources needed; are they structured and well documented or heterogeneous with limited information on their format and content
- What is the language in use in the data sources
- What is the expected output in terms of content and format

Based on this information, the AIDAVA team will be able to confirm additional work needed to develop missing components (see Section 3.2)

Reusable from AIDAVA: Template for data flows

3.1.2 Ethical approval, including Data Privacy and Data Privacy Officer (DPO) approval

AIDAVA is processing fully identifiable data to generate either identifiable data (e.g. patient IPS) or population pseudonymised or anonymized data. As a consequence, **compliance with GDP** must be ensured; this typically requires consent from the patient. While solutions for smooth electronic consent management are available, ethical and data privacy guidelines for daily use solutions like AIDAVA are not yet clearly spelled out and a request to a local Ethics Committee might be required to ensure DPO approval for deployment.

Notes:

- *AIDAVA can also work with pseudonymized and anonymized data. In this case EC approval might not be needed*
- *If EC approval is required and patient data are identifiable, we advise to include in the submission, the authorisation for the AIDAVA developers (UM, GND, AVER) to have access to patient identifiable data available in the local servers for debugging purposes.*

Reusable from AIDAVA: As part of the structured research protocol developed to obtain local Ethics Committee approval, the AIDAVA project team developed supporting material including

- Information Governance Framework and Instruments supporting Data Protection Assessment (DPIA) [\[ref\]](#)
- Study Information Package explaining the objective of the prototype to the patients and validated by the patient consultants to ensure understandability of the language [\[ref\]](#)
- Informed Consent Form
- Training material [\[ref\]](#)

This material can be provided in support of the request for Ethical approval.

3.1.3 Catalogue of data source : data source description (Data Transfer Specification)

To support automation, the AIDAVA prototype requires a detailed **data description of each data source** to be collected within the Catalogue of Data Sources¹⁸. This includes technical metadata on schema representation as well as FAIR metadata on context. This information is most often not readily available by lack of documentation, while staff with the needed expertise and knowledge are not easily accessible.

Reusable from AIDAVA: AIDAVA developed a template format [\[ref\]](#) with instructions on how to fill the template. **This template MUST be reused** to ensure proper functioning of mapping tools; in addition the first step in the curation is a validation check on this DTS to ensure that the format has been properly used.

3.2 Development

Some tasks—indicated in orange in the table below must be executed for any use case. Other ones are dependent on the use case.

The G2 prototype includes

- 2 Therapeutic areas: Breast Cancer, Cardiovascular disease;;
- 3 languages: Estonian, Dutch, German;
- curation of multimodal data including EHR data in scope of the 2 therapeutic areas, imaging (mammography and echo-cardiography), GP data, Blood Pressure Monitoring device and Quality of Life through a PROMS;

¹⁸ The catalogue follow the DCAT-AP specification and is a richer description—in terms of schema representation—of the TEHDAS Data Description for Data Holders, under [public consultation](#) in February 2025

- 3 outputs: International Patient Summary (IPS in HL7 FHIR format), computation of patient SMART CVD risk score and local BC registry including 80 data elements identified by the AIDAVA oncologists in OMOP/SNOMED format

Any use case extending the scope of the prototype in terms of therapeutic areas, language or type of data will require development as described in the table below.

Task	Description
Setup test environment	Setup a test environment to store mappings and test with TEST data from the clinical site
Ontology update	Check if there is a need to add of concepts relevant to the therapeutic area in scope of the use case; additions will be done in compliance with the Simplified Upper Level Ontology maintained by the AIDAVA team
Additional DQ checks	AIDAVA provides a set of checks—in the forms of SHACL language—supporting compliance to the ontology but also compliance to the domain. Specific checks can be added to increase the quality of the resulting curated PHKG
Data Extract (ETL) of sources	AIDAVA needs the data sources in the format specified in the Data Source Catalogue and provided through the Data Transfer Specification (DTS) . Data sources must be extracted from the local repository and provided in the DTS format. This would typically require an Extract Transformation Load (ETL) routine to extract information for the local database, transform it into the DTS format and load it into a secure local data store. The input variables for the ETL is the identifier (or set of identifiers) of the patient from which data must be extracted, as well as the period of extraction. We recommend to extract data from the moment the patient registered within the organisation.
Mapping	All data sources provided in the Data Transfer Specification (see Section 3.1.3) need to be mapped with the reference ontology in case of structured data or with a curation workflow (e.g. NLP or entity linking in the case of unstructured or semi-structured data). AIDAVA developed a mapping tool to support this process and reduce human variability across data scientists (and therefore reduce the risk of decrease interoperability)
Front end translation	The AIDAVA front end will requires translation if another language is being used
Translation of MIDATA HDI	The MIDATA front end will requires translation if another language is being used; MIDATA Health Data Intermediary is being used to manage non hospital data: GP, Withings BPM devices and EQ5D QLY trough BrightFish PROMS.
Integration MIDATA HDI	MIDATA integration will require Data Sharing Agreement with the local hospital and integration of the format in use in the national system managing GP documents.
NLP—other language	Any other language will require an adapted NLP model to process this language. If available this software will need to be checked and tested following the corresponding integration specification and testing [document available on demand] If not readily available two strategies might be followed <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Translation of the source into German or English (lower reliability, lower cost) • Annotation of document and retraining of available model (higher reliability, higher cost)
Entity Linking	Same as for NLP integration specification and testing [document available on demand]
Output generation (SPARQL)	The published output from AIDAVA needs to be adapted to the needs of the use case; this requires updates or development to the SPARQL query extracting information from the PHKG. Additional transformation or computation might be needed

Table 2. Needed development tasks before deploying AIDAVA
Color code: orange = must do task; green = needed if TA is different;
cyan = needed if MIDATA HDI is needed for non hospital data; grey = needed if language is different

3.3 Deployment

Task	Description
Infrastructure	AIDAVA is deployed LOCALLY by GND to ensure data remains in a local secure environment under the control of the organisation (see technical specification in Annexe)
Training patients and curators	<p>Before deploying the system, the local site must identify the patient in scope—and for which the data will be curated—and the data curators that will support them.</p> <p>Note: in case of pseudonymized or anonymized data, only the data curators must be identified.</p> <p>Once identified,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> the patients (if relevant in case of identifiable data) must be introduced to the system, with the SIP and sign an ICF; they also must follow an training on how to use the tool (see Section 3.1.2 for available material) the curators must be trained on the tool
Extract of data from patient and copy into AIDAVA	Once AIDAVA is deployed (typically within 1 day after the infrastructure is deployed), the local site must run the ETL module mentioned above in Section 3.2 to extract the data sources for the identified patient and load them into the AIDAVA secure data server.
Executing the curation	<p>Once the data are loaded, patients and curators can download their data and curate them, answering questions whenever needed.</p> <p><i>Note: in the G1 prototype about 40% of the data sources were automatically curated and answers to questions took on average 20 minutes (as computed by the system) per source document. These parameters are suboptimal and not acceptable; they should be seriously improved in G2.</i></p> <p>A support system (8/5) with a log tool will be deployed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Level 1 will be provided by the local sites in local language as a first contact point to the user. Any question that cannot be answer by the local site will be sent to Level 2 Level 2 will be provided by GND in English. Any question that cannot be solved by GND—typically on a specific component will be forward to the responsible partner. Level 3 will be provided by GND and other developers in English and based on the problem at hand.
Using the output	This is specific for each use case

Table 2. Needed tasks to deploy AIDAVA G2 prototype

Annexes.

Annex 1. Infrastructure requirement

This contains 2 components

1. NLP training environment to train the identified language model to the local language based on the output from the annotation process. This is optional, if the language model is already available
2. The Virtual Assistant environment

NLP Environment

Assumptions

- Pretraining the model for the medical domain + different languages, may occur at KU Leuven using their setup (2 RTX3090 and 4 NVIDIA TITAN Xp for the whole CS department) using public data
- Decentralised solution i.e. language models are training and applied locally
- Number of annotated documents for model training: < 20.000

Needed infrastructure

a. Hardware requirements for Health Discovery + NLP

Resources	Minimum	Recommended	Comments
CPUs / vCPUs	4 core	8 core	Depending on the degree of parallel processing
RAM	24 GB	64 GB	Depending on the degree of parallel processing
Disk Storage (Hard Drive)	1TB	4TB	Storage requirements depend on how many documents are imported.
GPU RAM	24GB RAM on a single GPU	A100 with 40GB RAM	The NLP models will run on the GPU. The general rule is that more GPU RAM allows us to train / apply more powerful models. While it is hard to foresee the development of LLM at the time being, we currently see smaller models that can be utilised with about 24 GB RAM (e.g. OpenLLama-7B with half precision, OpenLLaMA-3B with full precision). Hence, the minimal requirement is a single GPU card with 24 GB RAM per site (e.g. A30 for server-grade or 3090 (24GB) for customer-grade), but it would be better to have a more powerful A100.

- b. The machine learning models will also be loaded within a Docker container and will be started together with the Health Discovery in a Docker Compose context. Hence, we need a Docker installation
- c. (SSH) access for the machine learning experts for each individual site to conduct the model training

Virtual Assistant environment

Assumptions

- The architecture is based on G2 = individual dockerized version to support pluggability of curation tools...
- Volume of a PHKG for a single patient for 10 years is expected to be 80 MB * 10¹⁹

Needed infrastructure

- All required components of the prototype (services, databases, workflows, knowledge graph) will be loaded into Docker containers and it will be handled by our docker-compose file, docker installation is required
- SSH access to containers
- Https access will be required to access api endpoint from outside of hospital environment to run federated queries
- Hospital certificate what we could load into the prototype
- Mail server access to send notifications to the users

Hardware specification

Resources	Minimum	Recommended	Comments
CPUs / vCPUs	4 core	8 core	AVX Feature support is mandatory
RAM	64 GB	128GB	More than 50 containers running in parallel
Storage	512 GB	1 TB	Storage requirements depend on how many documents are imported.
GPU	Depends on selected model		We have a new potential tool (QuestionRephraser) which requires running an LLM model

Software specification

Software	Version	Comments
OS	Ubuntu server LTS 22	Container support is better on ubuntu
SSH Access		
Administrator access		For configuration
HTTPS Certificate		Wildcard certificate *.aidava.xxx
Sub-Domain		Wildcard subdomain is needed *.aidava.xxx
Mail Server		1 account to send notifications for patients and curators

FAQ

Question	Answer
Does AIDAVA run in AZURE cloud	Yes it does—It is already running in AZURE Cloud Services of one of the AIDAVA partner (cloud of national health services)

¹⁹ <https://www.harmonyhit.com/health-data-volumes-skyrocket-legacy-data-archives-rise-hie/>

Question	Answer

Annex 2. Customer Support

The following table provide a list of services that could be deployed to support the use of AIDAVA in clinical sites, in agreement with the AIDAVA partners

- The support requires opening of a log system
- The local Site Admin is the personal responsible locally for the configuration and set up of the system and the key contact for local users in their local language

Level	WHO	WHAT	HOW
L1	Local Site Admin	<p>Initial level of support provided to users locally – taking into account local constraints and data privacy. It typically involves basic troubleshooting and issue resolution. The goal is to resolve customer issues as quickly and efficiently as possible</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Answer common questions, provide instructions, or direct customers to self-help resources. • User management: add, update or delete user profiles <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Register new user – including personal address – with role and respective access rights; allocate users to roles ○ Take care of users who forgot their password • Log request in Issue Log when not possible to solve the problem directly, and follow up on resolution <p>Note: to send an email from the local site, the AIDAVA local system needs to have access to the local email server (or to have a local account from the hospital email system)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transfer issue to level 2 when not possible to solve locally 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal email, chat, or phone • Local language • 8 to 5 local time, working days <p>Input in Issue Log, required when transferring to L2</p>
L2	GND	<p>Involves more complex issue resolution and may require specialised technical knowledge or expertise. Level 2 support is usually provided by a specialised team, such as a technical support team or an engineering team, and may involve more in-depth troubleshooting or debugging</p> <p>Note: need access to the local version: console level access / IP Secure access with admin rights for maintenance purposes => GND will be an agreed stakeholder (as defined in the Study Protocol)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Email and GND phone (remote support with local access) • English • Working days – 8 to 5 local times (CET and CET + 1) = 8 to 6 (CET+1) for GND
L3	GND	<p>Involves the most complex and critical issue resolution, such as bug fixes or product enhancements. Level 3 support is usually provided by the product development team or senior technical experts and may involve code changes or product updates.</p>	<p>(NOT 24/7)</p>
L2	HDI	<p>For issues related to access to personal records (IPS) sent to the HDI</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Email • English • Working days – 8 to 5 local times (CET and CET + 1)

Function	Description	Value (min-max)
Issue Log	Centralised Service management system to be provided by GND to register and track all the issues	GND will provide a central issue tracking system to collect and supervise the issues reported during the evaluation and feedback phase. Also we will provide an issue collector page into the system, which will let the users create issue tickets directly into the tracking system.

Function	Description	Value (min-max)
Time to resolution	Time it takes between the first entry of an issue in the log file and the resolution	4 hours in average (for the tools developed by GND, no engagement for tools developed by other parties such as curation tools)

Annex 3. List of project deliverables

The table below provides the list of deliverables of the project, with the link—when available—to the deliverable itself, either in Zenodo or within the AIDAVA Google Drive for internal deliverables.

- Deliverables in white are not directly related to the deployment
- Deliverables highlighted in green are enabler for the development of AIDAVA
- Deliverables highlighted in cyan are core for the deployment of AIDAVA to external partners with limited/no adaptation outside configuration
- Deliverables highlighted in blue are core for the deployment of AIDAVA to external partners and are expected to require adaptation (other language, other TA)

N°	Deliverable name	WP	Lead	Type ²⁰	Diss. ²¹	Mth	Link
D1.1	Description of use cases	1	NEMC	R	PU	Jul 24	Zenodo
D1.2	Report from user survey with personas canvas	1	MUG	R	PU	May23	Zenodo
D1.3	Business requirements for G1	1	MUG	R	PU	Jul 23	Zenodo
D1.4	Definition of assessment study including test scenarios & metrics, and study initiation package	1	NEMC	R	PU	Jul 24	Zenodo
D1.5	ELSI templates filled in each site including midterm recruitment report	1	IHD	R	SEN	Jun 24	Request
D1.6	G1 installed for testing across all organisations	1	GND	DEM	SEN	Aug24	Request
D1.7	Report on G1 performance against benchmarks	1	NEMC	R	SEN	Jan 25	Request
D1.8	Update of Report (D1.2) from user survey with personas canvas	1	MUG	R	PU	Jan25	Zenodo
D1.9	Update of Business requirements (D1.3) for G2	1	MUG	R	PU	Mar25	Zenodo
D1.10	G2 installed for testing across all organisations	1	GND	DEM	SEN	Dec25	
D1.11	Report on G2 performance against G1	1	NEMC	R	SEN	Mar26	
D1.12	Report on the status of posting results in a repository	1	NEMC	R	PU	Mar26	
D2.1	Global Data Sharing Standard	2	Onto	DEM	PU	Jul 24	Zenodo
D2.2	Details on data curation & publishing process	2	UM	DEM	SEN	Aug23	Request
D2.3	Solution Design Document for G1	2	UM	DEM	PU	Jul 24	Zenodo
D2.4	Update of Solution Design Document (D2.3) for G2	2	UM	DEM	PU	May25	
D3.1	VA architecture (Application and Technical)	3	GND	DEM	PU	Jul24	Zenodo

²⁰ **Type:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action):

R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
 DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
 DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

²¹ **Dissemination level:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action)

PU: Public, fully open, e.g. web
 SEN: Sensitive, limited under conditions of the Grant Agreement

N°	Deliverable name	WP	Lead	Type ²⁰	Diss. ²¹	Mth	Link
D3.2	Epics and user stories for G1	3	GND	R	SEN	Nov23	Request
D3.3	Populated Data Source catalogue for testing	3	GND	DEM	SEN	Jul24	Request
D3.4	Populated library of FAIRification tools for G1	3	UM	DEM	SEN	May24	Request
D3.5	Imaging data curation tools in library for G1	3	UM	DEM	SEN	Mar24	Request
D3.6	G1 of the AIDAVA prototype	3	GND	DEM	PU	Jul 24	Zenodo
D3.7	Update of Epics and user stories (D3.2) for G2	3	GND	DEM	PU	Sep 25	
D3.8	Populated library of FAIRification tools for G2	3	GND	DEM	SEN	Oct25	
D3.9	Imaging data curation tools updated for G2	3	UM	DEM	SEN	Oct25	
D3.10	G2 of the AIDAVA prototype	3	GND	DEM	PU	Nov25	
D4.1	Annotation guidelines, tools & training	4	MUG	DEM	PU	Jan 2023	Zenodo
D4.2	Data Management Plan	4	IHD	DMP	PU	Feb 23	Zenodo
D4.3	Update to Annotation guidelines, tools & training	4	MUG	DEM	PU	Jul 23	Zenodo
D4.4	Information governance framework and instruments	4	IHD	Ethic	PU	Sep 23	Zenodo
D4.5	Report 1 from external Ethics Advisory Board (including names and CVs of member)	4	IHD	Ethic	PU	Apr 24	Zenodo
D4.6	Definition on data quality & performance metrics	4	IHD	R	PU	Jul 24	Zenodo
D4.7	Annotated datasets (3 languages/2 TA) with report	4	MUG	DATA	SEN	May 24	Request
D4.8	Regulatory conformance analysis of the AI development pipeline	4	IHD	Ethic	PU	Jan 25	Zenodo
D4.9	Report 2 from external Ethics Advisory Board	4	IHD	Ethic	PU	Jun 25	
D4.10	Update of the Data Management Plan	4	IHD	DMP	PU	Dec 25	
D4.11	Report 3 from external Ethics Advisory Board	4	IHD	Ethic	PU	Feb 26	
D4.12	Proposed operating model for HDI	4	IHD	Ethic	PU	Aug26	
D5.1	Data quality check services	5	UM	DEM	SEN	Jul 24	Request
D5.2	Analysis on explainability for different skill levels; delivery of explainability module for G2	5	MUG	R	SEN	Jan 25	Request
D5.3	Novel DL based tools to extract concept from clinical text and generate multimodal PHKG	5	AVER	OTH	SEN	Oct 24	Request
D5.4	Novel ML based FAIRification tools to harmonise and enhance structured data into PHKG	5	UM	DEM	SEN	Jan 25	Request
D5.5	KG Embedding algorithms	5	UM	DEM	SEN	Jan 25	Request
D5.6	Human-AI interface pattern library for G2	5	MUG	OTH	SEN	Oct 25	

N°	Deliverable name	WP	Lead	Type ²⁰	Diss. ²¹	Mth	Link
D5.7	Assessment report (& prototype) for multi-lingual approach	5	KUL	DEM	PU	Nov25	
D5.8	Update of the Novel DL based tools to extract concept from clinical text and generate multimodal PHKG	5	AVER	DEM	SEN	Nov25	
D5.9	Update of the Novel ML based FAIRification tools to harmonise & enhance structured data into PHKG	5	UM	DEM	SEN	Nov25	
D5.10	Update of the Data quality check services	5	UM	DEM	SEN	Nov25	
D5.11	Update of the KG Embedding algorithms	5	UM	DEM	SEN	Nov25	
D5.12	Causability report and impact on explainability	5	MUG	R	PU	Mar26	
D6.1	Public project website	6	EURICE	DEC	PU	Dec 22	Website, Zenodo
D6.2	Plan for dissemination & exploitation of results incl. communication (PDEC), updates in official report	6	EUR	R	SEN	Feb 23	Request
D6.3	IP Manual	6	EURICE	R	SEN	Feb 23	Request
D6.4	Communication Toolkit	6	EURICE	R	PU	Apr23	Zenodo
D6.5	Audio-visual material	6	EURICE	DEC	PU	Mar 24	Video, Zenodo
D6.6	Update of PDEC - official report 1	6	EURICE	R	SEN	Jul 24	Request
D6.7	Report on dissemination and communication activities	6	Onto	R	PU	Mar 24	Zenodo
D6.8	Recommendations from SAB	6	Onto	R	SEN	Jan 25	Request
D6.9	Update of PDEC - official report 2	6	EUR	R	SEN	Aug 25	
D6.10	Update of Report on dissemination and communication activities 1	6	Onto	R	PU	Aug 25	
D6.11	Update of Report on dissemination and communication activities 2	6	Onto	R	PU	Aug 26	
D6.12	Update of PDEC - official report 3	6	EURICE	R	SEN	Aug 26	
D6.13	Updated SAB Recommendations	6	Onto	R	SEN	Aug 26	
D7.1	Project Management Platform	7	EURICE	DEC	SEN	Nov 22	Restrict
D7.2	Management Guide	7	EURICE	R	SEN	Dec 22	Restrict
D7.3	Risk Management & Mitigation Plan	7	EURICE	R	SEN	4Dec 22	Restrict
D7.4	Internal progress report 1	7	EURICE	R	SEN	Nov 23	Restrict
D7.5	Internal progress report 2	7	EURICE	R	SEN	Feb 25	Restrict
D7.6	Results Ownership List Agreement	7	EURICE	R	SEN	Aug 26	